

**POLLUTION AS A VIOLATION OF ENVIRONMENTAL RIGHTS: A CRITICAL
ANALYSIS OF THE DILEMMA OF DELIVERING ENVIRONMENTAL JUSTICE
IN NIGERIA**

BY

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UG/19/0950

**FACULTY OF LAW
NIGER DELTA UNIVERSITY
WILBERFORCE ISLAND
BAYELSA STATE**

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**BEING A PROJECT SUBMITTED TO THE FACULTY OF LAW, NIGER DELTA
UNIVERSITY IN PARTIAL FULFILMENT OF REQUIREMENT OF THE AWARD
OF BACHELOR OF LAWS (LL.B) DEGREE OF NIGER DELTA UNIVERSITY
WILBERFORCE ISLAND BAYELSA STATE**

MAY 2025

DECLARATION

I, **INIMO-ETELE, GLORY BEINMOTEI**, hereby declare that this project which has been appropriately referenced with accredited works of other authors is my original work and is the product of my research efforts and it has neither been submitted in whole nor part for the award of a degree at this university or any other institution or university.

INIMO-ETELE GLORY BEINMOTEI

DATE

CERTIFICATION

This research study on “Pollution as a Tool for the Violation of Environmental Rights: A Critical Analysis of the Dilemma of Delivering Environmental Justice in Nigeria” has been approved in partial fulfilment of the requirement for the award of Bachelor of Laws (LL.B) Degree of Niger Delta University, Wilberforce Island, Bayelsa State.

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DEDICATION

To Almighty God, for His preservation, protection, wisdom, inspiration and for being the source of my strength, without you, this journey would not have been possible. To my lovely parents, Mr. Clarkson Inimo-Etele and Mrs. Racheal Sisigbogibene Etele, and my beloved grandmother, H.R.M Late Mrs. Ebiangasuo Christiana Dogood-Atoni, I dedicate this long essay/academic writing to you for being the inspiration behind it.

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The National Environmental Standards and Regulations (Enforcement) Agency (NESREA) Act, 2007

The Oil in Navigable Waters Act 1969 - Cap 337 LFN 1968 No. 34

Universal Declaration of Human Rights, 1948

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

AC.....	Appeal Cases
ACHPRA.....	African Charter on Human and People's Rights Act
AHRLR.....	African Human Rights Law Reports
CA.....	Court Of Appeal
CCA.....	Criminal Code Act
CEPA.....	Canadian Environmental Protection Act
CFCS.....	Chlorofluorocarbons
CFRN.....	Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria
FEPA.....	Federal Environmental Protection Agency Act
FHC.....	Federal High Court
FREP.....	Fundamental Rights (Enforcement Procedure) Rules
FRN.....	Federal Republic of Nigeria
GDP.....	Gross Domestic Product
ICCPR.....	International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights
ICESCR.....	International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights
ICJ.....	International Court Of Justice
LPELR.....	Law Pavilion Electronic Law Report
NDDC.....	Niger Delta Development Commission
NESREA.....	National Environmental Standards and Regulations Enforcement Agency
NGO.....	Non-Governmental Organization

NNPC.....Nigerian National Petroleum Company
NOSDRA.....National Oil Spill Detection and Response Agency
NOUN.....National Open University of Nigeria
NWLR.....Nigerian Weekly Law Report
OMPADEC.....Oil Mineral Producing Areas Development Commission
REDD+.....Reducing Emissions from Deforestation and Forest Degradation
SC.....Supreme Court
SHC.....State High Court
UDHRUniversal Declaration of Human Right
UNO.....United Nations Organization
WLR.....Weekly Law Reports
WRN.....Weekly Reports of Nigeria

ABSTRACT

In Nigeria, environmental pollution is one of the biggest factors contributing to an unhealthy environment for residents in different areas. In most common law systems, environmental liability has developed from actions under tort to fundamental human rights actions. Nevertheless, it is logical to imagine that an unhealthy environment will have negative impacts on lives and property, which are protected fundamental rights in most countries. Many Nigerians thus, often claim, in response to shocking environmental pollution incidents and disasters that such events violate their rights to a clean environment. However, victims of this harm have been unable to get justice because there is no explicit provision in the constitution that recognizes environmental rights. This paper examines whether environmental rights can be enforced via fundamental rights actions under Chapter IV of the Nigerian Constitution. It further examines environmental liability which is as a result of environmental pollution, from a human rights perspective and analyzes constitutional, statutory and judicial precedents with a view of determining what the state of law in Nigeria is on the subject. This paper concludes that environmental rights in Nigeria are still enforceable as fundamental rights, even though they are not explicitly listed as a Chapter IV constitutional right. To enforce these rights, applicants can plead facts and furnish evidence showing how the environmental act or omissions deprive people of their lives and property. Another route for enforcement of environmental rights as a fundamental rights action is by bringing an African Charter Act action to enforce the fundamental right to general satisfactory environment which is described as a fundamental right by the Fundamental Rights (Enforcement Procedure) Rules.

CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background to the Study

The issue of environmental rights is a vital and essential aspect of ensuring a healthy and sustainable relationship between humans and their environment. Conversely, environmental pollution constitutes a violation of these rights, often resulting from human activities and exploitation of natural resources.¹ In his interaction with nature, man regards all non-human living organisms as means to an end. Humans have a tendency to harm the environment in pursuit of economic gain and sustainability. Man is always ignorant of the very important fact that we should have a clear way of doing things so that we do not degrade the environment, because environment is the most important aspect of our everyday lives and degrading it will amount to harming ourselves. In essence, we have a moral responsibility to protect the environment especially in our respect for the integrity of natural ecosystem, preservation of the endangered species and prevention of environmental pollution.² It is true that human beings have many rights of which include economic, cleanliness of the environment, the use of the natural resources and the improvement of the standards of living. Apart from the fact that man's survival depends on the survival of the non-human organisms, environment also has its own rights of which man has to respect. The environmental rights include the protection of the natural resources, renewable and non-renewable, the sustainable use of the natural resources and the protection of all the nonhuman organisms.³ The issue of

¹OP Sunday, 'The Conflict Between Environmental Rights and Human Rights: A Panacea' (2008) 3(1) *INJODEMAR* <<https://www.ajol.info/index.php/ijdmr/article/view/47948/34315>> accessed 3 August, 2024

² Ibid

³ Ibid

environmental pollution became glaring worldwide and in the continent of Africa respectively shortly after the 1972 United Nations Conference on Human Environment at Stockholm where it was not only confirmed the emergence of environmental protection as a new focus of legislation so as to avoid crisis but equally emphasized the close inter relation between the environment and development. It is unfortunate that, this area of environmental studies has not been given adequate attention by many developing countries, although, their actions may be due largely to ignorance on the parts of government and people as to its relevance. In developing countries, most of the environmental problems are caused by under development. Subsequently, in 1992, the UNO's Earth Summit in Rio de Janeiro in Brazil emphasized the close relationship between the environment and development. And the development must be sustainable by meeting the needs and aspirations of the current generation without compromising the ability to meet those of future generation. Environmental problems particularly in Nigeria only came to the limelight after the dumping of toxic waste in Koko, Delta State in 1988. This was corroborated in an article written by P. Smith and A George entitled 'The Dumping Grounds No 94' South Magazine. It was the response of the Federal Military Government to this incident that led to promulgation of the Federal Environmental Protection Agency Act, 1988 and the Harmful Waste (Special Criminal Provision) Act of 1988. Subsequently in 1989, the Government issued official gazette on National Policy on the Environment.⁴ Nigeria is one of the developing countries of Africa therefore, the country is not exempted with different environmental problems facing their third world counterpart and even the advanced nations of the world experienced the same problems. The total and practical lack of effective regulatory policies on hazardous

⁴ AA Taiwo, 'Environmental Law' (National Open University of Nigeria) <<https://nou.edu.ng/coursewarecontent/LAW%20321%20Environmental%20Law%201.pdf>> accessed 3 August, 2024

wastes management and lack of monitoring system in place on environmental issues in the early eighties made the country susceptible recipient of surreptitiously exported ‘Transboundary hazardous waste dump by developed and industrialized countries’. In the majority of common law regimes, environmental liability has evolved from tort proceedings to basic rights actions. Between these developments, legislatures in common law countries adopted and revised statutes governing environmental liability and enforcement. It is reasonable to expect that an unhealthy environment will have a negative impact on people and property, both of which are protected as fundamental rights in most countries. It is also beneficial for a system to have numerous paths for enforcing good environmental policies and processes.⁵

Every human is reliant on their living environment. To the fullest extent possible, a safe, clean, healthy, and sustainable environment is essential for the realization of several human rights, such as the rights to food, water, life, health, and sanitation. We cannot achieve our goals in the absence of a healthy atmosphere. The relationship between environmental protection and human rights has gained a lot of attention in recent years. There is a significant increase in the quantity and breadth of national and international laws, court rulings, and scholarly research on the subject of human rights and the environment. However, a number of issues regarding the interplay between environment and human rights remain unresolved. Human rights and the environment are intrinsically intertwined: a safe, clean, healthy and sustainable environment is essential in the enjoyment of our human rights; whilst polluted, hazardous and otherwise unhealthy environments potentially violate our human rights.

⁵A Babalola, ‘The Right to a Clean Environment in Nigeria: A Fundamental Right?’ (2020) 26(1) *HELJ* <https://repository.uclawsf.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=1576&context=hastings_environmental_law_journal> accessed 3 August, 2024

Environmental rights mean any proclamation of a human right to environmental conditions of a specified quality. This means that they are not abstract, remote, irrelevant concepts; they are measurable, prominent and functional aspects of society and its ecology. More than 100 countries incorporate constitutional rights to a healthy environment. When environmental rights are violated, people and the planet suffer from reduced health and well-being.⁶ The catastrophic repercussions of environmental crises are being felt by people more and more across the world. These effects range from the loss of land, biodiversity, and livelihoods, to extreme weather, food shortages, and health problems related to air and water pollution.⁷ Despite myriad international agreements, as well as national laws and policies, the condition of our environment keeps deteriorating.

In this project, the researcher will take a closer look at the Nigeria legal system, including environmental right and pollution principles and specific statutes that come into play when it comes to environmental liability cases. Throughout the study, the researcher will discuss the enforceability of environmental rights in Nigeria, examining court decisions, potential challenges, and any limitations that may arise. The researcher will also consider how the Nigerian legal framework compares to other jurisdiction in terms of addressing environmental rights breach claims. The researcher will analyze the impact that environmental pollution can have on individuals, looking at both the legal and social implications. This research study examines whether environmental rights can be enforced via fundamental rights action under Chapter IV of the Nigerian Constitution. It examines

⁶Geneva Environment Network, ‘Human Rights and the Environment’ <<https://www.genevaenvironmentnetwork.org/resources/updates/human-rights-and-the-environment/>> accessed 19 July, 2024

⁷ Human Rights Watch, ‘Environment and Human Rights’ <<https://www.hrw.org/topic/environment>> accessed 20 July, 2024

environmental liability from a human rights perspective and analyzes constitutional, statutory, and judicial precedents with a view of determining what the state of the law in Nigeria is on the subject. The research study will conclude that, though the right to a clean and protected environment is not explicitly listed as a Chapter IV constitutional right, environmental rights are still enforceable as fundamental rights in Nigeria. Lastly, the researcher will explore the available remedies for victims of environmental pollution, discussing the legal options individuals have to seek justice and potential reforms that could improve the current system.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

It is worthy to note that due to the advent of environmental pollution, the effects results to environmental liability. For a long time, environmental liability in Nigeria, a country with a rich common law heritage, was regulated under the auspices of the law of torts. In addition to common law, new system of environmental regulation and liability through federal and state regulation and enforcement was introduced to Nigeria through the enactment and subsequent amendments of environmental statutes and the creation of environmental agencies. These environmental statutes and agencies regulate water resources, harmful waste, air, parks, vehicular emissions, forests, land use, animals, pests, mining, hides and skins, oil pipelines and nuclear safety. There is still a lot of work that needs to be done to make Nigerian cities resilient to climate changes, air pollution and flood. For instance, states like Lagos, Bayelsa, Makurdi, etc. have had devastating floods that could have been contained to some extent by proper urban planning. These floods led to loss of lives and properties, and the displacement of numerous residents and businesses. Cross River State is taking giant steps to adapt to the effects of climate change through its REDD+ program, which stands for “Reducing

Emissions from Deforestation and Forest Degradation.” Quite recently, the government of Cross River State declared July 30th as a public holiday for the planting of one million trees in a ceremony known as the Green Carnival.⁸

Environmental pollution is a violation of human rights due to man-made or human-aided alteration of the environment's chemical, physical, or biological quality. Nigeria's laws and regulations on pollution control are not elaborate enough to address complex subject matters, particularly in the oil industry. The Constitution vests original jurisdiction for the enforcement of fundamental rights action in the High Court of a State where any provision of Chapter IV is being or likely to be contravened. The Constitution does not explicitly provide for a specific provision for environmental rights. However, certain provisions in the Constitution can be interpreted as encompassing environmental concerns. Section 20 of the CFRN 1999⁹ as amended states that, ‘The State shall protect and improve the environment and safeguard the water, air and land, forest and wild life of Nigeria.’ However, there have been a number of debates that the aforementioned section is not justiciable by virtue of Section 6 (6) (c) of the CFRN 1999 as amended. Nigeria still relies on common law remedies for dealing with environmental liability, rather than as a violation of fundamental rights or human rights.¹⁰ The present study, therefore, seeks to fill this gap in knowledge that environmental liability is crucial to realizing the broader version of environmental rights. Certain provisions in the Constitution can be interpreted as encompassing environmental concerns, for example, Section 20 of the CFRN 1999 as amended. However, there have been

⁸ A Babalola (n5)

⁹ CFRN 1999

¹⁰ AA Taiwo, ‘Environmental Law II’ (National Open University of Nigeria) <<https://nou.edu.ng/coursewarecontent/Law%20322%20ENVIRONMENTAL%20LAW%20II.pdf>> accessed 20 July, 2024

a number of debates that the aforementioned section is not justiciable by virtue of Section 6(6) (c) of the CFRN 1999 as amended. Thus, Nigeria today, still relies on common law remedies in dealing with environmental liability and not as a violation of fundamental human rights.

1.3 Research Questions

1. To what extent do the courts in Nigeria enforce claims in environmental rights violation as fundamental rights breach?
2. What are the challenges of the enforceability of environmental rights violation in Nigeria for victims seeking legal recourse for fundamental rights breach?
3. To what extent are the existing legal frameworks effective in curbing environmental pollution and protecting environmental rights?
4. What are the challenges and limitations associated with the remedies available to victims of environmental rights violations seeking legal redress for breaches of fundamental rights?

1.4 Aim and Objectives of the Study

The central aim of the study is to examine the enforceability of environmental rights violation as fundamental rights breach. This focus stems from the increasing recognition that environmental pollution can directly infringe on core human rights such as the right to life, health, dignity and even property. This study therefore aims to explore how violations of environmental rights could be reframed as violations of legally enforceable fundamental rights, such as the right to life (Section 33 of the CFRN 1999 as amended) or the right to dignity (Section 34). By connecting environmental degradation to violations of constitutionally protected human rights, litigants have tried to get around the non-

justiciability barrier and obtain justice through judicial interpretation and litigation strategy, particularly with instruments like the Fundamental Rights (Enforcement Procedure) Rules, 2009. The specific objectives are:

1. To examine the extent at which the courts in Nigeria enforce claims in environmental right violation as a fundamental right breach.
2. To examine the challenges of the enforceability of environmental rights violation in Nigeria for victims seeking legal recourse for fundamental rights breach.
3. Examine the existing legal framework's effectiveness in curbing environmental pollution and protecting environmental rights.
4. To examine the challenges and limitations associated with the remedies available to victims of environmental rights violations seeking legal redress for breaches of fundamental rights.

1.5 Scope and Limitations of the Study

The study examines the challenges of the breach of environmental rights in Nigeria. However, the study focuses on the effect of environmental pollution and the enforceability of environmental liability and pollution as fundamental right breach in Nigeria. The research is limited by legal, ecological and socio-economic factors. The numerous limitations encountered in the course of this research work include deficient power supply, financial constraints, time limitations, scarcity of resources. The study acknowledges but not comprehensively addresses all the nuances, requiring careful consideration of regional variations. This study is limited by lack of cases specifically for the breach of environmental rights. The study relies on potentially missing unreported incidents, reported cases and legal

reports. Nevertheless, the researcher persevered and successfully completed the study despite these obstacles.

1.6 Significance of the Study

The study is significant because, knowledge derived from the study will create awareness for the protection of the environment. The study is significant because it will provide a comprehensive analysis of enforceability of environmental rights actions in the context of fundamental rights. Lastly, findings from the study can inform policymakers and legislators in Nigeria about potential gaps or areas for improvement in existing legal frameworks and the knowledge may contribute to the development of more effective and nuanced policies concerning environmental liability or pollution, aligning them with contemporary societal expectations.

1.7 Research Methodology

This study will adopt the doctrinal research method in conducting the present research. The doctrinal research method is primarily about investigation and discussion of legal principles and legal proposition. Such research relies largely on analysis and interpretation of statutes and case law as primary source of data, whiles journals, textbooks, articles, dictionaries and other sources provides the secondary data for the study. The study's choice of the doctrinal method is justified on the basis of the nature of the research topic and importance of the study which is to scrutinize the challenges of enforcing environmental rights actions as fundamental rights breach and environmental pollution as a violation of human rights.

1.8 Synopsis of the Chapters

The research work contains five chapters. In chapter 1, the research study sets the context by looking at the background to the study, the statement of the problem, research questions which gives directions to the research work, the aims and objectives of the study, scope and limitations, the significant of the study, the research methodology employed and the synopsis of the chapters. Chapter 2 critically looks at the conceptual framework by explaining and analyzing the major concepts in the study and the historical development of the study. It also conducts a thorough review of existing literature review on environment, pollution, environmental pollution, environmental rights and human rights in Nigeria. It synthesizes scholarly works, research articles, and theoretical frameworks to provide a comprehensive understanding of the history and evolution of human rights, history of environmental pollution and environmental rights, human right theory, the effect of environmental pollution on the breach of human/fundamental rights. The literature review identifies gaps in knowledge, such as the lack of the enforcement of environmental rights claims in Nigeria, the effect of environmental pollution by analyzing various limitations to the enforceability of environmental rights actions. This chapter 2 aims to contribute valuable insights to the discourse on the enforceability of human rights in Nigeria. Chapter 3 encompasses the legal and institutional framework surrounding environmental rights protection in other jurisdictions and in Nigeria. It analyzes institution governing environmental rights protection particularly the enforceability of the environmental rights claim as fundamental rights breach in Nigeria. By exploring the legal and institutional frameworks in place, this chapter aims to provide a comprehensive overview of the regulatory framework affecting environmental rights and pollution in Nigeria. In chapter 4, it presents the discussions of the research study on concept

of the enforceability of environmental rights in Nigeria; environmental rights infringement in Nigeria and the legal implications under the Nigerian law as well as the challenges that are faced in the process of enforcing these rights, the remedies, why these rights are not as important as civil rights and the constitutional provision for the enforcement of environmental rights in other climes in comparison to Nigeria. In Chapter 5 which is the final chapter summarizes the key findings of the research study and presents conclusions drawn from the analysis of the legal framework for environmental pollution, environmental rights enforcement and protection in Nigeria. It provides recommendations for enforceability of environmental rights violations as fundamental rights breach. The chapter concludes by emphasizing the importance of the right to a healthy environment at all times.

CHAPTER TWO

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Conceptual Framework

2.1.1 What is Environment?

The concept of environment is highly technical, making it difficult to define universally. Environmental academics have attempted to define the term in various ways. The term 'Environment' is formulated on the word 'Environ' derived from the French work 'Environner', which means 'to surround' or 'to encircle'.¹ Generally, it is defined as our surroundings especially material and spiritual influences which affect the growth, development and existence of living being. The United Nation Stockholm Conference on Human Development asserts 'man is both creature and moulders' of his environment, which gives him physical sustenance and affords him the opportunity for intellectual, moral, social and spiritual growth². Although, these definitions has been criticized as anthropocentric in nature. This is so because, other organisms that inhabits the environment were relegated to the background. According to the Black's Law Dictionary³, the environment is the milieu in which an organism lives; it includes the sum of all of its surroundings. This includes natural forces and other living things. It defines the conditions of danger and damage to existence, as well as development and growth.⁴ The environment includes all or any of the following media; air, water and land and any living organisms (including humans) or ecosystems supported by

¹ A Kumar, 'Brief Introduction of Environment, Ecology and Environmental Pollution' (2018) 8(1) *JMME* <<https://inspirajournals.com/uploads/Issues/159348613.pdf>> accessed 24 October 2024

² Preamble to the Report of the United Nations Conference on Human Development and Environment, 1972 particularly paragraph 1) <<https://digitallibrary.un.org/record/523249?ln=en&v=pdf>> accessed 16 May 2025

³ Black's Law Dictionary, 2nd Edn <<https://thelawdictionary.org/environment/#:~:text=Definition%20and%20Citations%20Approach>> accessed 16 May 2025

⁴ The Law Dictionary, 'Environment: Definition and Legal Meaning' <<https://thelawdictionary.org/environment/>> accessed 20 October 2024

those media.⁵ The concept of the environment in Nigeria would ultimately determine the need for and the scope of the law in seeking to control, regulate and where possible prevent various forms of environmental hazards and pollution. The environment has been defined as, ‘the totality of physical, economic, cultural, aesthetic and social circumstances and factors which surround and affect the desirability and value of property and which also affect the quality of peoples’ lives.’⁶ Although, the definition given above views the environment as a condition of nature as seen holistically and as the setting in which humans live in their natural habitat. ‘The conditions and influences of the place in which an organism lives’⁷ is another definition of the environment that can lend some credence to this statement. All living and non-living things found in the atmosphere, water, and earth shall be considered organisms in this definition, along with people, animals, and plants.⁸ For purposes of law, the environment has been defined as the system of abiotic, biotic and socio-economic components with which man interacts and simultaneously to which he adapts and transforms and uses in order to satisfy his needs.⁹

Einstein once remarked; ‘The environment is everything that isn’t me’. However, ‘environment’ has now taken on a rather more specific meaning, though still a very vague and general one, and may be treated as covering the physical surroundings that are common to all of us including air, space, wastes, land, plants and wildlife. The encompassing nature of

⁵ LexisNexis, ‘Environment Definition’ <<https://www.lexisnexis.co.uk/legal/glossary/environment>> accessed 20 October 2024

⁶ AA Taiwo, ‘Environmental Law II’ (National Open University of Nigeria) <<https://nou.edu.ng/coursewarecontent/Law%20322%20ENVIRONMENTAL%20LAW%20II.pdf>> accessed 20 July, 2024

⁷ Cambridge Encyclopedia, ‘Environment’ <<https://dictionary.cambridge.org/dictionary/english/environment>> accessed 16 May 2025

⁸ L Atsegbua, V Akpotaire, and F Dimowo, *Environmental Law in Nigeria: Theory and Practice* (2nd Edn, AMBIK Press, 2010) 3

⁹ Ibid 4

the term has also been emphasized by the International Court of Justice in its advisory opinion on the *Legality of the Threat or Use of Nuclear Weapons*¹⁰. In the case of *A.G Lagos State v A.G. Federation*¹¹, the term ‘environment’ connotes the natural conditions, for example land, air and water, in which people, animals and plants live.¹² The National Environmental Standards and Regulations (Enforcement) Agency Act, 2007 defines ‘environment as including water, air, land and all plants and human beings or animals living therein and the inter-relationship which exist among these or any of them’.¹³ In a nutshell, the term ‘environment’ refers to the full spectrum of living and non-living elements that affect life on Earth and how they interact. It is crucial for human survival and is impacted by factors like poverty, urbanization, population growth, and technology. The need for legislation to protect the environment is highlighted due to its complex causes and effects.¹⁴

2.1.2 What is Pollution?

Pollution is assumed to be a relative concept because although almost no substance exists in pure state, it is only when the impurities rise above a certain level that it became dangerous and harmful. Pollution is the introduction of contaminants into the natural environment that causes adverse change. Pollution can take the form of any substance (solid, liquid, or gas) or energy (such as radioactivity, heat, sound, or light).¹⁵ Pollution is the introduction of substances or energy (such as light or heat) into the natural environment in amounts or concentrations that can be harmful for humans, animals, and plants. As early as 1924, at a

¹⁰ Advisory Opinion, ICJ Rep, 1996, 241f, para 29

¹¹ (2003) 2 NWLR (Pt 833) 1

¹² Ibid

¹³ Section 37 NESREA Act 2007

¹⁴ L Atsegbua, V Akpotaire, and F Dimowo (n8)

¹⁵ Wikipedia, ‘Pollution’ <<https://en.m.wikipedia.org/wiki/Pollution>> accessed 24 October 2024

conference of the International law Association, ‘pollution’ of the Sea was defined as: ‘an act whereby the inoffensive use of the water becomes impossible either for animal life or human use, or create a danger to such life or such use’. According to Hodge, pollution is the introduction of substances or energy liable to cause hazard to human health, harm to living resources and ecological system, damage to structure or amenities or interference with legitimate use of the environment. For example, noise, smoke, car emissions, chemical affluent in seas and rivers particularly sewage and household waste (all contribute to greenhouse effect).¹⁶ Section 34 of the NESREA Act 2007 defines pollution as man-made or man-aided alteration of chemical, physical or biological quality of the environment to the extent that is detrimental to that environment beyond acceptable limits. The 1972 United Nations Conference at Stockholm defines pollution as ‘the discharge of toxic substances and the release of heat, in such quantities or concentrations as to exceed the capacity of the environment to render them harmless’. According to Black’s Law Dictionary, pollution is the presence of harmful substances (either physical or gaseous), noise or energy (radiation) within a certain area, that causes harm to the surroundings, altering the natural environment around which it has been excreted.¹⁷ From the various definitions above, one can see that pollution ought to encompass air, land and sea.¹⁸

Nigeria's oil prospecting operations are a major source of pollution, particularly in the Niger Delta's oil-producing villages. Oil contamination causes blowouts, spills, and destruction

¹⁶ AA Taiwo, ‘Environmental Law I’ (NOUN) <<https://nou.edu.ng/coursewarecontent/LAW%20321%20Environmental%20Law%201.pdf>> Accessed 24 October 2024 116-117

¹⁷ Black’s Law Dictionary, 2nd Edn <<https://thelawdictionary.org/pollution/#:~:text= POLLUTION%20Definition%20%26%20Legal%20Meaning&text=The%20presence%20of%20harmful%20substances,which%20it%20has%20been%20excreted>> Accessed 24 October 2024.

¹⁸ AA Taiwo (n16)

from gas flaring, causing 25% of land in the Delta region to be barren. Offshore oil deposits also contaminate beaches. Environmental hazards include pollution of water, gas flares, and land, as well as socio-economic disequilibrium. Despite these environmental damages, the sale of crude oil provides a significant revenue source for the country.¹⁹ Pollution harms ecosystems by harming or even killing living things. The severity of pollution depends on the pollutant, its characteristics, and location. Pollutants can be solid waste, radioactive waste, heat, gaseous pollution, metals, and inorganic compounds. They can come from foreign substances or naturally occurring contaminants and cause air, land, and water pollution.²⁰

2.1.3 Types and Sources of Pollution

There are many types and sources of pollution which can be differentiated on the basis of the nature of the pollutant and they shall be treated on the basis on how they affect human life.

Water Pollution

Water is crucial for life, covering 71% of the Earth's surface. 97% is in oceans, while 3% is freshwater. Only 0.003% is easily available as soil moisture, groundwater, water vapor, and water in lakes, streams, rivers, and wetlands.²¹ Water is essential for all living forms, domestic purposes, industry, agriculture, tourism, recreational activities, transportation and fishing. However, urbanization, industrialization, and population growth have led to a decline in water availability, resulting in pollution and negative health impacts. Mismanagement of industrial effluents and improper waste disposal has damaged coastal water. Water pollution,

¹⁹ L Atsegbua, V Akpotaire, and F Dimowo (n8) 93-96

²⁰ Ibid

²¹ Dr. Rajendra Prasad Central Agricultural University 'Study Material on Water Pollution: Causes, Effects and Control Measures' <<https://www.rpcau.ac.in/wp-content/uploads/2020/03/Water-Pollution.pdf>> accessed 27 October 2024

caused by human activities like fishing, is the introduction of harmful substances into marine environments, affecting water quality and amenities. Water pollution, caused by industrialization and population growth, is a harmful contamination of water bodies, affecting life through toxicity, killing plants and animals, and causing reproductive failure, primarily from oil spills, industrial refuse, and agricultural fertilizers.²²

The World Bank report “Towards the Development of an Environmental Action Plan for Nigeria” identified water pollution as the second highest potential for future negative impact on the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) (estimated at US \$1 billion annually) and puts 40 million people at risk.²³ In Nigeria, industrial influences such as direct liquid waste discharges, solid waste dumping into water bodies, and careless hazardous waste disposal are causing increasing issues with surface and ground water quality, even though agricultural and municipal waste account for the majority of water pollution. In the case of industrial pollution, the major water pollution concerns are suspended solids, pH, oil and grease, heavy metals and elevated temperature. Waste water treatment plants are virtually non-existent, and sludge and liquid wastes are typically deposited in open drains, sewer system and water bodies without any treatment. The treatment plants that have been built are usually inadequate for the volume and type of waste they are expected to treat, or else they have broken down. The main type of water pollution in Nigeria, especially in the riverine areas is oil pollution. This affects the life of the people, ecosystems etc. For example, it had been scientifically proven that:

When used motor oil is poured on the ground, it can seep down to the ground water and contaminate drinking water supplies. A single quart of oil can pollute 250,000 gallons of drinking water. Also,

²² United Nations Group of Experts on Scientific Aspects of Marine Pollution in 1969 <<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0025326X23013528>> accessed 16 May 2025

²³ L Atsegbua, V Akpotaire, and F Dimowo, (n8) 98-99

Pouring oil into the sewer or on the street where it will eventually wash into the sewer is like pouring it directly into a stream or a river, and just one pint of used motor oil can produce a poisonous slick an acre in diameter.²⁴

According to late Professor Ambrose Alli:

As a result of oil loses, vast tracks of agricultural land have been laid waste, thus becoming unproductive, surface water and river courses are invariably contaminated and polluted, rendering the water undrinkable, and the aquatic life is destroyed. The result is great hardship for the inhabitants who become impoverished and deprived. These unfortunate citizens are therefore compelled to migrate to other towns and villages in search of decent life.²⁵

Thus, oil spills can result in health hazards to human beings and can also cause fire outbreaks, constituting extensive damage to life and property. In Nigeria for example, between 1976 and 1980, over 56 million gallons of oil spilled into the Nigeria environment especially the marine environment.²⁶

Noise Pollution

According to A.S. Hornby, noise is a sound, especially when it is loud, unpleasant or disturbing. Noise can be described as unwanted or unbearable, excessive sound. Be that as it may, 'noise pollution' seems to have been taken for granted and in fact accepted by most people in the society especially in this part of the world. Economic growth and prosperity has no doubt led to an upsurge in the source of noise pollution world over. The ignorance of the health hazard of noise may be the sole reason for nonchalant attitude of people towards noise pollution. Noise pollution from ship engines and solar systems make it difficult for marine mammals like whales, dolphins and porpoises to communicate, find food, and avoid hazards. Powerful solar systems operating at certain frequencies have been implicated in whale beaching and may cause damage to marine mammal sound-sensitive internal structures,

²⁴ Ibid 100

²⁵ AO Salu, 'Securing Environmental Protection in the Nigerian Oil Industry' (1999) *MPJFIL* 3(2) 337; L Atsegbua, V Akpotaire, and F Dimowo (n8) 101

²⁶ Ibid

causing internal bleeding and even death. Frequent or chronic exposure to both high and low intensity sound may cause stress on all higher forms of marine life, potentially affecting growth, reproduction and liability to resist disease. Some sources of noise pollution include; Motor vehicle noise, noise generated by the religious houses, boat engines, road traffic noise, noise from construction sites, noise emission from industries, mechanic and welder workshops' noise, etc.²⁷

Air Pollution

Air, a mixture of gases, primarily consists of gases surrounding the Earth's thin layer, which is about 95% above sea level. Air pollution occurs within the first two kilometers of the tripe sphere region. Pollution generally is endemic and constitutes hindrance to all living organisms on earth and the earth's ecosystem which in turn affects the air constituents. Air pollution can be defined as the pollution caused by substances released into the air by human activities in such concentration which is sufficient to cause harmful effects to human health, vegetables, property or to interfere with the enjoyment of property. According to Lawrence Atsegbua, 'air pollution is the upsetting of the natural arrangement of different gases in the air.' In a nutshell, it is the presence of foreign bodies in the air such as gaseous, particulate or a combination of all, which is highly hazardous to the health, sustenance and welfare of man.²⁸ The sources of air pollution refer to the various locations, activities or factors which are responsible for the releasing of pollutants in the air.²⁹

²⁷ AA Taiwo (n16)

²⁸ Ibid

²⁹ Ibid

Land Pollution

Pollution of land in a broad sense can clearly arise from licensed as well as unlicensed activities, although in many cases, pollution of land is just one part of licensed activities. For example, the potential for pollution of soil is one consideration amongst many under the integrated pollution prevention and control regime. More obviously, the disposal of waste to landfill involves direct pollution of land itself. The term land pollution equally includes anything laid in land which automatically impairs its arableness, yield or cultivability such as land mines, booby traps and other similar military devices.³⁰ Without prevarication, the major cause of land pollution in Nigeria and other parts of the world particularly in the millennium age can be traced to development of technology, that is, industrialization which led to the bursting of urbanization and the over concentration of the world population in the areas of the landmass. In addition, land pollution could also be in form of solid waste and has been defined as 'non - liquid, non - soluble materials hanging from municipal garbage to industrial wastes that contain complex substances and sometimes hazardous substances'. One of the identified pollutants linked with petrochemical industries are effluence. This effluence contains a wide range of organic and inorganic contaminants such as phenol, oil, gas, and toxic metals, hydrogen sulphide and ammonia. Others are quarrying, mining of all sorts, causes damage to the environment on a large scale. Therefore, it is unthinkable now to move away from the part of industrialization. In this wise, there arises a necessity for evolving a scheme for balancing the needs of industrialization and curbing the evils of hazardous

³⁰ Ibid

substances and industrial processes causing human health hazards and environmental pollution.³¹

2.1.4 What is Environmental Pollution?

Environmental pollution has emerged as one of the most pressing challenges of the 21st century. The issue has led to threats to human health, ecosystems, and the overall well-being of our planet. Environmental pollution is therefore defined as the introduction of any substance in such characteristic and for such duration as to produce a deleterious effect on all living things in an area in terms of their viability, relative abundance, health, morality, etc.³²

Environmental pollution refers to the introduction of harmful materials into the environment. In other words, environmental pollution is the contamination of the physical and biological components of the environment to such an extent that normal environmental processes are adversely affected.³³ Environmental pollution means “an undesirable change in the environment through harmful substances; waste materials and resources, caused by man’s activity or natural disaster which also results to the degradation of the environment with its attendant consequences on biodiversity.”³⁴

Effects of Pollution on the Environment

The environment is considered polluted when it is altered in composition or condition directly or indirectly as a result of the activities of man so that it becomes less suitable for some or all of the uses for which it is suitable in its natural state. The health implications of

³¹ Ibid

³² L Atsegbua, V Akpotaire, and F Dimowo (n8) 97

³³ NEXT IAS, ‘Environmental Pollution: Types, Causes, Consequences and More’ <<https://www.nextias.com/blog/environment-pollution/>> accessed 17 December, 2024

³⁴ MI Evelyn and TT Tyav, ‘Environmental Pollution In Nigeria: The Need For Awareness Creation For Sustainable Development’(2012) 2(4) *AJOL* <<https://www.ajol.info/index.php/jrfwe/article/download/84726/75830>> accessed 17 December 2024

pollution in society are very obvious, because environmental pollution destroy the physical, mental: and social well-being of man. Lung diseases are contracted from inhaled dust, skin disease from allergic material and toxic wastes released into the atmosphere. There is a systematic effect on the human body, which occurs when a toxic substance has been absorbed into the bloodstream and distributed throughout the body. Disturbances may' be caused in several parts of the body such as the blood, nervous system, kidney, liver and skin. A Polish weekly magazine 'Pryjacioika' noted that noise pollution causes fatigue, impaired concentration and insomnia. Apart from the direct effect on man, environmental pollution has several direct consequences on humanity, by destroying ecological balances (environmental catastrophe). In *Minimata Japan*, people eating fish polluted by mercury. This resulted in 120 dead and numerous injuries.³⁵ Deforestation is taking place at alarming rate, and while millions of trees are cut in one year, it sometimes issue of ozone depletion and global warming. The earth is being stripped of its vegetation and animal life is dying of starvation. Another effect of pollution is the effect of oil pollution on a local environment, which can be very severe and persistent, sometimes lasting unaltered for decades, and the consequences are usually enormous on the ecosystem. This depletion of ozone is linked to the use of Chlorofluorocarbons (CFCs). The creation of greenhouse gases and the depletion of the ozone layer are worldwide problems, which require international co-operation to be solved. The effects of pollution of the environment and its victims are far-reaching and completely devastating. Although it may not be possible to completely avoid pollution, it is possible to control it.³⁶

³⁵ L Atsegbua, V Akpotaire, and F Dimowo (n8)

³⁶ Ibid 118-120

2.1.5 What are Rights/ Human Rights?

Rights are legal, social, or ethical principles of freedom or entitlement; that is, rights are the fundamental normative rules about what is allowed of people or owed to people according to some legal system, social convention, or ethical theory.³⁷ Rights are justified claims or entitlements to the carrying out of correlative duties, positive or negative. Omoregbe defines rights as ‘a justifiable claim to anything any privilege or immunity to which one is entitled’. A claim to a right requires carrying out a duty, and no claim can be made without reference to the law that grants it. Rights are defined by terms like fulfillment, infringement, overridden, and absolute. Fulfillment occurs when the correlative duty is fulfilled, while infringement occurs when the correlative duty is not fulfilled. Overridden rights are justifiably infringed, while absolute rights cannot be overridden and must be fulfilled without exceptions. Human rights have been described as the rights that exist for every human being for the simple fact of humanity. Human rights are universally recognized moral principles or norms that establish standards of human behavior and are often protected by both national and international laws. These rights are considered inherent and inalienable, meaning they belong to every individual simply by virtue of being human, regardless of characteristics like nationality, ethnicity, religion, or socio-economic status. They encompass a broad range of civil, political, economic, social, and cultural rights, such as the right to life, freedom of expression, protection against enslavement, and right to education.³⁸ We have different types of rights but all of them are broadly grouped into two namely: Civil rights and Fundamental human rights which are also called natural right. However, focus will be made on fundamental human rights.

³⁷ Wikipedia, ‘Rights’ <<https://en.m.wikipedia.org/wiki/Rights>> accessed 17 December, 2024

³⁸ Wikipedia, Human Rights’ <https://en.m.wikipedia.org/wiki/Human_rights> accessed 27 December 2024

Fundamental Human Rights

Fundamental human rights have come to be understood as the rights which are universally attributable to man regardless of his social and political antecedents and also, his biological and psychological limitations. These rights are variously referred to by different scholars as universal rights, basic rights, moral rights, etc. When we talk of fundamental human rights, we mean the rights conferred on man by nature. These are the rights of individuals to live according to their natural condition. So, fundamental human rights are those rights which are inherent in our nature and without which we cannot live as human beings. These are the rights that are indispensably necessary for man to fulfill his potential on this earth.³⁹ In the case of *Akinosun v COP, Kwara State & Ors*, the court held Per Ibrahim Mohammed Musa Saulawa, JCA:

By virtue of the provisions of Order 1 Rule 2 of the Fundamental Rights (Enforcement Procedure) Rules, 2009⁴⁰, the term fundamental and human right denotes: Any of the rights provided for in Chapter IV of the Constitution and includes any of the rights stipulated in the African Charter on Human and People's Rights (Ratification and Enforcement) Act.⁴¹

This definition was reiterated in plethora of cases such as *Ashiru & Ors v Isah*⁴², *Osondu & Anor v A.G Enugu State & Ors*⁴³, etc. Fundamental human rights allow us to fully develop and use our human qualities, our intelligence, our talents and our conscience and to satisfy our spiritual and other needs. They are based on mankind's increasing demand for a life in which the inherent dignity and worth of each human being will receive respect and protection. These are the rights that every human being, irrespective of race, creed, sex, political leaning or religion ought to enjoy. The fundamental human rights are based on the

³⁹ OP Sunday, 'The Conflict Between Environmental Rights and Human Rights: A Panacea' (2008) 3(1) *INJODEMAR* <<https://www.ajol.info/index.php/ijdmr/article/download/47948/34315>> accessed 11 April 2025

⁴⁰ FREPR 2009

⁴¹ (2020) LPELR-49739(CA)

⁴² (2022) LPELR-58311(CA)

⁴³ (2017) LPELR-43096(CA)

right to own one's self, to think for one's self and to act on one's choices. A society can only be said to be free if it respects fundamental human rights. In this case, the society would allow people the total freedom to act provided the exercising of one's right does not constitute hindrance to the rights of others. No one loses an element of one's rights or surrenders them because of coercion but the person still retains one's natural rights.⁴⁴ On the whole, the point must be made at this juncture that the main objective of fundamental human rights is to secure for individuals the necessary conditions for leading a minimally good life. This aspiration has been enshrined in various declarations and legal conventions issued during the past fifty years, initiated by the Universal Declaration of Human Rights (1948) and perpetuated by, most importantly, the International Covenant on Civil and Economic Rights (1966).⁴⁵ These rights are contained in Chapter IV of CFRN 1999 as amended. The United Nations in their 1948 Universal Declaration of Human Rights held these rights sacred and regarded them as the foundation upon which the edifice of world peace could be built. So the violation of these rights is a threat to world peace because these rights are based on human nature. These rights constitute the foundation of peaceful co-existence and happiness of mankind. Even Governments have no right to violate these rights by legislation. No wonder, Paton submitted that Fundamental Human Rights 'are beyond the powers of the state'. These rights 'are more intrinsic and more fundamental than legal rights that are superficial, which, may exist today and disappear tomorrow'.⁴⁶

The underlying current message in this paper is that there has been unending conflict between the rights of the environment and that of man. This conflict is not caused by the environment

⁴⁴ Ibid

⁴⁵ OP Sunday (n39)

⁴⁶ Ibid

but by man as a result of the egoistic tendencies in man. Man thinks of himself alone and how life could be easier for him. Man regards the environment as tool in his hand which he can treat in any manner provided it does not affect man's desire for comfortable life even though the environment suffers for it. All things that have to do with nature such as land, plants, animals, water and the totality of the environment are treated with levity. They are only given consideration provided they are useful in helping man to satisfy his selfish end. The fact of the matter is that if the environment is not secure, man is not secure as his continued existence as a living being could not be guaranteed due to the destruction of the ecological support system for a continued life. So, the best thing to do is to put up programmes to secure the environment which would in turn secure human lives and rights.⁴⁷

2.1.6 What are Environmental Rights?

Environmental rights, also known as the human rights or constitutional rights that are used for the protection of the environment, have proliferated over the last 45 years. Environmental rights mean access to the unspoiled natural resources that enable survival, including land, shelter, food, water and air. They also include more purely ecological rights, including the right for a certain beetle to survive or the right for an individual to enjoy an unspoiled landscape. Environmental rights are human rights, as people's livelihoods, their health, and sometimes their very existence depend upon the quality of and their access to the surrounding environment as well as the recognition of their rights to information, participation, security and redress.⁴⁸ According to United Nations Environment Programme, Environmental rights mean any proclamation of a human right to environmental conditions of a specified

⁴⁷ Ibid

⁴⁸ FOEI, 'Environmental Rights are Human Rights' <<https://www.foei.org/environmental-rights-are-human-rights/>> accessed 27 December 2024

quality. Environmental rights are the protection of natural resources; the access to and use of natural resources; and how the access to and use of these resources affects surrounding populations, as well as the resources themselves.⁴⁹ The right to a clean environment is a fundamental human right that requires a healthy, balanced environment and sound resource management. Enacting environmental rights would grant the public a right to a healthy environment, increase private citizens' protection from pollution, and grant access to information and participation in standard settings.⁵⁰

2.2 Theoretical Framework

2.2.1 Human Right Theory

Human rights theory is based on the idea that all people have inherent rights that are universal and inalienable, meaning they cannot be taken away. John Locke (1689) developed the theory that every human being has certain rights that derive from their own nature and not from their government or its laws.⁵¹ The idea that these natural rights should entitle people to certain legal protections became more widely accepted and began to be reflected in the constitutions of some countries. These rights are indivisible and interdependent, and include a wide range of civil, political, economic, social, and cultural rights. Here are some key aspects of human rights theory, these are:

⁴⁹ UNEP, 'What are Environmental Rights?' <<https://www.unep.org/explore-topics/environmental-rights-and-governance/what-we-do/advancing-environmental-rights/what#:~:text=Environmental%20rights%20means%20any%20proclamation,conditions%20of%20a%20specified%20quality>> accessed 27 December 2024

⁵⁰ Ibid

⁵¹ Council of Europe, 'Compass: Manual for Human Rights Education with Young People' <<https://www.coe.int/en/web/compass/what-are-human-rights->> accessed 28 December 2024

- i. Universal: Human rights are the same for everyone, regardless of race, gender, nationality, ethnicity, religion, or other status. This simply means that they apply equally to all people everywhere in the world, and with no time limit.
- ii. Inalienable: Human rights are inherent to every person and cannot be taken away. This means that you cannot lose them, because they are linked to the very fact of human existence, they are inherent to all human beings. In particular circumstances some – though not all – may be suspended or restricted.
- iii. Indivisible and interdependent: All human rights are equally important and cannot be fully enjoyed without the others. This means that different human rights are intrinsically connected and cannot be viewed in isolation from each other.
- iv. Protected by law: Human rights are often protected by national and international laws.
- v. Moral order: Human rights are based on the idea that there is a moral order that applies to all people everywhere and at all times.⁵²

This theory plays an increasingly significant role in the enforcement of environmental rights in Nigeria, especially in light of challenges posed by constitutional and legal limitations such non-justiciability of environmental provisions in Chapter II of the CFRN 1999 as amended. Thus, this theory views environmental protection as a necessary condition for the enjoyment of fundamental human rights such as the right to life (Section 33) which includes the right to a clean and healthy environment, right to dignity (Section 34) and right to property (Section 43).

⁵² Supra

2.2.2 An Ecological Perspective to Change and Development

The viewpoint is linked to Wilkinson and Boulding's (1973) writings. The theory focusses on challenges of development and change in modern societies, particularly as they pertain to ecologically related population growth trends, environmental changes, and the need to establish and sort out methods of addressing development issues. According to the notion, as a society's population grows, its people place greater demands on its limited resources, including land and other natural resources, in order to survive. They engage in socioeconomic activities that pollute the environment and society and further damage (degrade) them, either directly or indirectly. This theory define socio-economic activities as the commercial and industrial activities of people in urban-industrialized civilizations of Western Europe and North America, as well as the subsistence agricultural activities of people in agrarian societies of Africa, Latin America, etc. The viewpoint also maintained that when a civilization outgrows its base of resources and productive system, progress is required. According to this viewpoint, societies are compelled to alter their practices as the long-standing economic system of a particular environment or society is shown to be insufficient and the productive system becomes increasingly troublesome. For example, as a society's population develops beyond its capacity, particularly in rural areas, people are compelled to relocate to cities in pursuit of employment. The establishment and operation of industrial activity by urban and city people pollutes society equally. According to Wilkinson and Boulding, these activities contaminate the environment either directly or indirectly, which has an impact on biodiversity.⁵³

⁵³ MI Evelyn and TT Tyav (n34)

2.3 Historical Foundation

2.3.1 The History and Evolution of Human Rights

Human rights are rights inherent to all human beings, regardless of our nationality, residence, sex, sexual orientation, national or ethnic origin, color, religion, language, or any other status. Originally, people had rights only because of their membership in a group, such as a family. In 539 BC, Cyrus the Great, after conquering the city of Babylon freed all slaves to return home. Moreover, he declared people should choose their own religion and establish racial equality. These and other principles were recorded on a baked-clay cylinder known as the Cyrus Cylinder. This clay tablet containing his statements is the first human rights declaration in history. Its provisions served as inspiration for the first four Articles of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights. The idea of human rights spread quickly to India, Greece and eventually Rome. This led to many statutes in regards to human rights. Another cornerstone in Human Rights History is represented by the promulgation of the Magna Carta in 1215, which brought a raw concept of 'Rule of Law' and the basic idea of specified rights and liberties to all persons, which offers protection from arbitrary prosecution and incarceration represents another cornerstone in the history of human rights. Prior to Magna Carta, the rule of law- now seen as a fundamental tenet of responsible government in any contemporary democratic society- was seen as a divine justice that could only be administered by the monarch, king, or in this case, King John of England. The Magna Carta gave people new rights and made the King subject to the law. An evolution of the concepts expressed by the Magna Carta is represented by the English Bill of Rights that was signed into law in 1689 by Williams III and Mary II, who became co-rulers in England after the overthrow of King James II which is credited as being an inspiration for the United States Bill of Rights (1791).

The Petition of Rights 1628 set out the rights of the people too. The United States Declaration of Independence 1776 proclaimed the right to life, liberty and the pursuit of happiness. The Declaration of the Rights of Man and of the Citizen, adopted in 1789, by France's National Assembly represents one of the basic charters of human liberties, containing the principles that inspired the French Revolution. This brought about the definition of civil and political rights. These rights are also known as first generation rights. The adoption of the first three Geneva Conventions and the Hague Convention emphasized the importance of promoting human dignity even during wartime. Human rights recognition and protection have grown immensely since the Second World War. The proliferation of international human rights instruments began in 1945 with the UN Charter, which established the rules governing the structure and operations of the United Nations. The Charter explicitly sought "to reaffirm faith in fundamental human rights, in the dignity and worth of human person." The United Nations Charter, signed in 1945, aimed to save future generations from war, reaffirm faith in fundamental human rights, and promote social progress and better standards of life. In 1948, the Commission on Human Rights was established to draft the Universal Declaration of Human Rights, which is now recognized and internationally accepted. This is the first document listing the thirty (30) rights to which everyone is entitled. This birthed the second-generation rights. Thus, the entrenchment of human rights advanced in 1948 with the Universal Declaration of Human Rights and in 1966 with the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights and the International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights. The concept of third-generation rights has been proposed as a result of a deeper understanding of the obstacles that may stand in the way of realizing first and second-generation rights. The third-generation of rights focuses on solidarity and collective rights,

such as sustainable development, peace, and a healthy environment. The fourth-generation, linked to rapid technology development. The international community is still discussing fourth-generation rights, but there may be room for the fifth and future generations of human rights.⁵⁴

2.3.2 The History of Environmental Pollution

From the oldest to the present, human-dominated ecological systems have been a part of environmental degradation history. This history is defined by a society's rising regional prosperity, followed by crises that either resolved and resulted in sustainability or did not, resulting in decline. The natural makeup of plant and animal groups may have changed in early human history due to the usage of fire and the need for particular foods. The emergence of agrarian societies between 8,000 and 12,000 years ago was primarily dependent on their surroundings and the development of a "structure of permanence". The enormous expansion potential of fossil fuel energy was harnessed throughout the Western Industrial Revolution of the 18th and 19th Centuries. Eventually, coal was used to create energy and power ever-more-efficient engines. Large populations were shielded from disease by modern sanitation systems and medical advancements. A growing environmental movement in the middle of the 20th century made the point that the numerous material advantages that were now being enjoyed came at a cost to the environment. By the end of the 20th century, environmental issues had spread over the world. The global community's dependence on non-renewable energy supplies was made evident by the energy crises of 1973 and 1979. By the 1970s, humankind's ecological footprint had surpassed the earth's carrying capacity, making

⁵⁴ M Sutto, 'Human Rights Evolution, A Brief History' The CoESPU Magazine (Italy, 23 December 2019)18 <<https://www.coespu.org/articles/human-rights-evolution-brief-history>> accessed 9 January 2025

humankind's way of life unsustainable. The threat posed by climate change, which is mostly caused by the combustion of fossil fuels, is becoming more widely recognized in the 21st century. The loss of biodiversity, which is mostly brought on by the changes in land use, is another serious issue.⁵⁵ In Nigeria, environmental issues did not become officially prominent until the 1988 Koko Toxic Waste Dumping scandal, which also highlighted the urgent need to establish the Federal Ministry of Environment, the Nigerian Federal Environmental Protection Agency (FEPA), and other pertinent agencies ostensibly to address environmental issues in the nation. Environmental pollution, sanitation, ozone layer depletion, desertification, flooding, erosion, poverty, bush burning, deforestation, soil conservation and so on are some of these problems. All of the aforementioned points indicate that environmental challenges, specifically environmental pollution, which is the subject of this study, have become crucial to Nigeria's growth.⁵⁶

2.3.3 The History and Evolution of Environmental Rights

Environmental rights are an extension of basic human rights, and a safe and sustainable environment is paramount. The history and evolution of environmental rights reflect humanity's growing awareness of the interconnectedness between a healthy environment and human well-being. The Industrial Revolution (18th -19th centuries) brought about rapid industrialization, urbanization, and environmental degradation. Pollution, deforestation, and resource exploitation highlighted the need for environmental protection. Scholars like Henry David Thoreau and John Muir in the United States emphasized the intrinsic value of nature and its protection. Early conservation movements emerged, leading to the establishment of

⁵⁵Wikipedia, 'History of Environmental Pollution' <https://en.m.wikipedia.org/wiki/History_of_environmental_pollution> accessed 8 January 2025

⁵⁶ MI Evelyn and TT Tyav (n44)

national parks, such as Yellowstone in the United States in 1872. Rapid industrialization after World War II caused widespread environmental degradation. This led to increased public awareness and the emergence of environmental science as a discipline. The Stockholm Declaration (1972), a United Nations Conference on Human Environment recognized the right to a healthy environment and marked the beginning of global environmental governance. Some countries (e.g., Portugal in 1976) began including environmental rights in their constitutions. Organizations like Greenpeace (founded in 1971) played a crucial role in raising awareness and advocating for environmental rights. The Rio Declaration and Agenda 21 emphasized global cooperation and individual countries' responsibilities for environmental protection. Also, the Kyoto Protocol, an international treaty to reduce greenhouse gas emissions, reflecting the global acknowledgement of environmental challenges like climate change. In the 21st century, issues such as climate change and biodiversity loss have pushed the concept of environmental rights into the global spotlight. In several countries, courts have ruled that the right to a healthy environment is an implicit human right. The United Nations General Assembly Resolution formally recognized access to a clean, healthy, and sustainable environment as a universal human right.⁵⁷ Thus, Nigeria's environmental rights have evolved through several stages, some of which are:

- i. Colonial period: From 1900-1956, Nigeria had little environmental legislation, with the exception of some public health and torts and nuisance law provisions.
- ii. Petroleum focused period: From 1957-early 1970s, Nigeria enacted sector specific legislation in response to the discovery and commercialization of crude oil.

⁵⁷ S Turner, 'Introduction: A Brief History of Environmental Rights and the Development of Standards' <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/332969880_Introduction_A_Brief_History_of_Environmental_Rights_and_the_Development_of_Standards> accessed 9 January 2025

- iii. Rudimentary legislation period: From the 1970s-pre-1987 crisis, Nigeria enacted laws in response to the oil boom, including the creation of river basin authorities and environmental units in some government ministries.
- iv. Contemporary period: From post-1987 to the present, Nigeria has enacted serious legislation, increased environmental awareness, and become more sophisticated.⁵⁸

The evolution of environmental rights reflects society's shifting priorities, recognizing that environmental protection is essential not only for ecological balance but also for safeguarding fundamental human rights.

2.4 Review of Related Literature

The enforcement of environmental rights has become a topic of growing interest among academics, decision-makers, and human rights activists. Legal provisions like Section 20 of the CFRN 1999 as amended which encompasses environmental concerns is not justiciable by virtue of Section 6 (6) (c) of the CFRN 1999 as amended. This study of the literature looks at the body of knowledge regarding the institutional and legal aspects that affect how successful these laws are. It looks at how Nigeria's several legal systems, which includes statutory laws, and institutions make it difficult to implement them consistently. This section offers a basis for comprehending the chances and gaps in guaranteeing the enforceability of environmental rights in Nigeria by examining various viewpoints and results from earlier studies.

Many academics/writers have debated on rule in *Rylands v Fletcher*⁵⁹ playing an interesting though somewhat limited role in the enforcement of environmental rights in Nigeria. In

⁵⁸ A Ogunba, 'An Appraisal of the Evolution of Environmental Legislation in Nigeria' (2016) 40 (3) *VLR* 673-694 <<https://lawreview.vermontlaw.edu/wp-content/uploads/2016/07/40VtLRev673-Ogunba.pdf>> accessed 9 January 2025

Nigeria, the rule has been used in civil litigation involving environmental harm, especially pollution. Although Chapter II of the Nigerian Constitution (Directive Principles) is non-justiciable, tort law — including the *Rylands v Fletcher* rule — gives individuals a way to privately enforce environmental rights, especially in property or nuisance-related disputes. In Nigeria, the rule in *Rylands v Fletcher* addresses environmental pollution and degradation from crude oil exploration and production, protecting the environment and compensating those affected by the destruction of livelihood. Consequently, the rule has been applied in various decided cases in Nigeria. In *Umudje v Shell BP Nig Ltd*⁶⁰, the plaintiff respondents claimed damages from the defendants/appellants for the “escape” of oil waste, which respondents alleged, had damaged their ponds and lakes and farmlands. The findings of the learned trial judge were that crude oil-waste previously collected in a pit burrowed by, and in the control of the appellants escaped into the adjoining hands of the respondents where it damaged the ponds and lakes in Unenurhe land and killed the fishes therein. On those facts, the Supreme Court held the appellants liable under the rule.

Ayodele Babalola in his article ‘The Right to a Clean Environment in Nigeria: A Fundamental Right?’ makes a strong case for recognizing and enforcing environmental rights through fundamental rights litigation under Chapter IV of the Nigerian Constitution. However, in doing so, the paper underplays or insufficiently addresses critical pitfalls in enforcing environmental rights specifically under Sections 33, 34, and 43 of the 1999 Constitution. While the paper argues that environmental rights can be enforced under Chapter IV of the CFRN 1999 as amended, however, it does not fully grapple with the judicial

⁵⁹ (1866) L.R. 1 Ex 265

⁶⁰ (1975) LCN/2005 SC

reluctance to expansively interpret these rights in the context of environmental degradation. The author supports the idea that environmental harm can infringe on the right to life. While this is theoretically valid, the paper fails to confront the absence of strong domestic precedents where Nigerian courts have interpreted environmental degradation as a violation of the right to life (beyond *Centre for Oil Pollution Watch v. NNPC*⁶¹, which was more about locus standi). It does not sufficiently address the burden of proof required to establish a causal link between environmental harm and a real or imminent threat to life—an evidentiary challenge courts are unlikely to easily overlook. The paper almost entirely ignores Section 34, which arguably could cover exposure to toxic waste, poor sanitation, or harmful living conditions as degrading treatment. This omission is significant because, the UN Human Rights Committee and other international bodies have interpreted dignity-based rights as inclusive of environmental factors. Nigerian courts, however, have not developed this jurisprudence, and the paper misses the opportunity to argue for this interpretive evolution or note the risks of its absence. The author suggests environmental harm can amount to an infringement on property rights. Yet, there's limited analysis on how Nigerian courts have treated this in the environmental context. The author does not explore how existing environmental laws (e.g., NESREA Act, Land Use Act) might limit or complicate claims under Section 43. The paper overlooks the tension between public interest (e.g., environmental regulations or urban planning) and individual property rights. Other Weaknesses in the Enforcement Argument is the non-justiciability of Chapter II and Its Spillover Effect. The article argues that the African Charter and the FREP Rules make Section 20 (Chapter II) justiciable by implication. This is controversial and not yet firmly

⁶¹ (2019) 5 NWLR (Pt 1666) 517

accepted in Nigerian jurisprudence. The paper does not adequately warn about the doctrinal uncertainty of trying to enforce socio-economic rights indirectly through Chapter IV.⁶²

Kaniye S.A. Ebeku in his article ‘The Right to a Satisfactory Environment and the African Commission’ provides a comprehensive critique of Nigeria’s environmental rights enforcement, particularly in the Niger Delta. However, it notably fails to engage with the enforcement potential of sections 33, 34, and 43 of the Nigerian Constitution, which could be powerful tools for environmental litigation. Section 33 guarantees the right to life, and courts in other jurisdictions have expansively interpreted this to include a right to a clean and safe environment. The article does not analyze how Nigerian courts could similarly evolve the interpretation of this right, particularly in the face of environmental degradation that threatens health and survival. The author discusses human rights broadly in relation to environmental harm but omits how section 33 can be directly invoked to challenge state and corporate conduct that leads to life-threatening pollution, such as oil spills and gas flaring. Section 34 protects the right to dignity and freedom from inhuman or degrading treatment. Environmental degradation—e.g., exposure to toxic waste or loss of means of livelihood through oil pollution—can violate human dignity. The article fails to connect these lived environmental injustices to violations of human dignity. Courts in India and Latin America have acknowledged such links, but the document remains silent on how Nigeria’s judiciary might use section 34 as a foundation for environmental justice. Section 43 ensures the right to own and enjoy property. In regions like the Niger Delta, environmental harm has directly

⁶² A Babalola, ‘The Right to a Clean Environment in Nigeria: A Fundamental Right?’ (2020) 26(1) *HELJ* <https://repository.uclawsf.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=1576&context=hastings_environmental_law_journal> accessed 3 August, 2024

interfered with the people's ability to use their land, fish, and farm—core to their property rights. While the paper highlights oil-induced environmental damage, it does not consider how victims could litigate under section 43 to claim compensation or injunctions for violation of property rights due to ecological destruction. The paper critiques the inadequacy of the environmental provisions under Chapter II (Directive Principles), especially section 20, which is non-justiciable. However, it misses the strategic legal pathway of interpreting enforceable rights (sections 33, 34, and 43) in an environmental context to circumvent this limitation. Scholars and practitioners have increasingly urged the reimagining of constitutional rights through an environmental lens—something this article doesn't explore, leaving a significant analytical vacuum. While the article does a commendable job analyzing the *SERAC v Nigeria case*⁶³ and the African Charter, it fails to capitalize on the legal leverage available under sections 33, 34, and 43 of Nigeria's Constitution. These provisions could serve as viable constitutional footholds for environmental claims but are left unexamined.⁶⁴

2.5 Gap in Knowledge

Environmental liability refers to the legal obligation to prevent, mitigate, and compensate for environmental damage caused by individuals, corporations, or governments. Despite its critical role in safeguarding environmental rights, knowledge gaps around environmental liability persist, hindering effective enforcement and public awareness. Environmental liability is an essential but often overlooked aspect of environmental rights. Addressing the knowledge gap in environmental liability is crucial to realizing the broader version of

⁶³ (2001) AHRLR 60

⁶⁴ KSA Ebeku, 'The Right to a Satisfactory Environment and The African Commission' (2003) 3 (1) *AHRLJ* <https://www.ahrlj.up.ac.za/images/ahrlj/2003/ahrlj_vol3_no1_2003_kaniye_sa_ebeku.pdf> Accessed 29 January 2025

environmental rights. The Constitution does not explicitly provide for a specific provision for environmental rights. However, certain provisions in the Constitution can be interpreted as encompassing environmental concerns. Section 20 of the CFRN 1999 as amended provides that, ‘The State shall protect and improve the environment and safeguard the water, air and land, forest and wild life of Nigeria.’⁶⁵ However, there have been a number of debates that the aforementioned section is not justiciable by virtue of Section 6 (6) (c) of the CFRN 1999 as amended. Nigeria today, still relies on common law remedies in dealing with environmental liability and not as a violation of fundamental rights/human rights. Common law remedies for environmental pollution in Nigeria are rooted in English common law principles, which Nigeria inherited during the colonial period. These remedies allow individuals or groups to seek redress for environmental harm through civil litigation. Some of which includes; nuisance, the rule in *Rylands v Fletcher*⁶⁶, negligence, etc. Thus, pollution occurs in relation to many uses and activities of man, including the mining, exploration and the use of petroleum and its by-products. In all these cases, there is damage to marine life, wildlife habitat, farmland, shrines, recreational beaches, property and other social amenities. It may also result in the contamination of drinking water and in some cases fire outbreaks. Apart from these instances, there are health hazards and threats to life, as well as the destruction of natural amenities upon which are based on the economic and social well-being of the inhabitants of these areas. The point at which a particular activity alters the environment and radically affects the way of life and economic well-being of those who live within its vicinity, or poses danger to their health and life, is the threshold at which pollution is a violation of environmental rights. Thus, the rights which environmental pollution affects

⁶⁵ CFRN 1999

⁶⁶ (1866) L.R. 1 EX 265

are numerous, some of which are: right to life, economic, social and cultural rights, right to health, right to dignity of human person, and right to property, etc.⁶⁷

⁶⁷ L Atsegbua, V Akpotaire, and F Dimowo (n8) 172-173

CHAPTER THREE

LEGAL AND INSTITUTIONAL FRAMEWORK

3.1 Legal Framework

No laws can save nature, it is only man himself that can do it, and so we have to change ourselves to protect nature and the environment through legislations and institutions set up for that purpose.¹

3.1.1 The National Environmental Standards and Regulations (Enforcement) Agency (NESREA) Act

The National Environmental Standards and Regulations (Enforcement) Agency Act repealed the Federal Environmental Protection Agency Act. This Act could be described as a great step towards improving other laws governing pollution and other forms of environmental degradation in the country. Section 27(1) of NESREA Act² prohibits the discharge in such harmful quantities of any hazardous substance into the waters of Nigeria or adjoining shorelines except as permitted or authorized by the law in force in Nigeria. Also the, “Agency shall make recommendations to the President, Commander in Chief of the Armed Forces for the purpose of establishing water quality standard for the inter-state waters of Nigeria to protect the public health or welfare and enhance the quality of water to serve the purpose of the Act.”³

3.1.2 The Criminal Code Act

The Criminal Code Act⁴ does not have a specific section dedicated exclusively to environmental pollution or environmental protection, as it is primarily focused on criminal

¹ L Atsegbua, V Akpotiare, and F Dimowo, *Environmental Law in Nigeria: Theory and Practice* (2nd Edn, AMBIK Press, 2010) 121

² NESREA 2007

³ L Atsegbua, V Akpotiare, and F Dimowo (n1) 109

⁴ Criminal Code Act Cap 38, Vol. 4 as CCA in force since 1961

offences like theft, assault, and fraud. The Criminal Code contains provisions for the prevention of public health hazards and for environmental protection. However, some provisions indirectly address acts that harm the environment under the broader context of public health, nuisance, or harm to public welfare. Below are the relevant sections:

- i. Section 234: This section criminalizes any act or omission that endangers the public or is injurious to public health. The release of toxic substances or contamination of water bodies can fall under this if it affects public health or creates widespread inconvenience.
- ii. Section 245: This section prohibits acts that render water unfit for human consumption or likely to cause injury or harm.
- iii. Section 247: This section applies to activities that create offensive smells or conditions hazardous to the health of the public. For example, improper disposal of waste by industries can fall under this section.

3.1.3 The Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria

The Constitution does not explicitly provide for a specific provision for environmental rights. Section 20 of the CFRN 1999 as amended provides that, ‘The State shall protect and improve the environment and safeguard the water, air and land, forest and wild life of Nigeria.’ The ‘right’ provided under this section is not justiciable by virtue of Section 6 (6) (c) of the CFRN 1999 as amended, it shall not except as otherwise provided by the Constitution, extend to any issue or question as to whether any act of omission by any authority or person or as to whether any law or any judicial decision is in conformity with the Fundamental Objectives and Directive Principles of State Policy set out in Chapter II of the Constitution. Though in the 1990s, the courts seemed to have made even the non-justiciable rights justiciable by

relying on the domestication of the African Charter, a regional instrument on Human Rights.

In *Uzoukwu v Ezeonu II*⁵, the Court of Appeal held inter alia that:

There are other rights which may pertain to a person which are neither fundamental nor justiciable in the court. These may include rights given by the Constitution as under the Fundamental Objectives and Directive Principles of State Policy under Chapter II of the Constitution.⁶

The judicial pronouncement on the rights under the Directive Principles provisions was re-echoed in *Abacha v Fawehinmi*⁷ where the Supreme Court, relied on the domestication of the African Charter in Nigeria and upheld the decision of the Court of Appeal.⁸ Section 12 of the CFRN 1999 as amended establishes, though impliedly, that international treaties (including environmental treaties) ratified by the National Assembly should be implemented as law in Nigeria. Sections 33 and 34 of the CFRN 1999 as amended which guarantee fundamental human rights to life and human dignity respectively, have also being argued to be linked to the need for a healthy and safe environment to give these rights effect.⁹

Nigerian courts have developed two significant exceptions to this principle of non-justiciability. The first exception arises when the National Assembly exercises its powers under Items 60(a) and 68 of the Exclusive Legislative List by enacting laws to “promote and enforce the observance of the Fundamental Objectives and Directive Principles” contained in Chapter II of the Constitution. When the National Assembly enacts legislation relating to Chapter II provisions pursuant to Items 60(a) and 68 of the Exclusive Legislative List, the courts have consistently held these provisions to be enforceable. The second exception occurs when Chapter II provisions are interpreted in conjunction with justiciable provisions of the Constitution, particularly the fundamental rights outlined in Chapter IV. In such circumstances, the provisions of Chapter II become enforceable. Beyond Section 20, the

⁵ (1991) 6 NWLR (Pt 200) 708

⁶ Supra

⁷ (1994) NWLR (Pt 306) 1

⁸ NG Ikpeze, ‘The Environment, Oil And Human Rights in Nigeria’ (2024) 2 (15) *NAUJILJ* <<https://www.ajol.info/index.php/naujilj/article/download/82388/72543>> Accessed 29 January 2025

⁹ Environmental Law Research Institute, ‘A Synopsis of Laws and Regulations on the Environment in Nigeria’ <<https://elri-ng.org/environmental-law-policies-in-nigeria/>> Accessed 29 January 2025

Constitution provides additional environmental protection through fundamental rights provisions. Section 33(1)'s right to life and Section 34(1)'s right to human dignity have been interpreted to encompass environmental protection.¹⁰

3.1.4 African Charter on Human and People's Rights (ACHPR)

The African Charter on Human and People's Rights (ACHPR), adopted in 1981 and in force since 1986, explicitly recognizes environmental rights. Article 24 provides that 'All peoples shall have the right to a general satisfactory environment favorable to their development'. Thus, this provision establishes a collective right to a healthy environment, emphasizing that environmental protection is not just an individual right but a people's right, aligning with the Charter's emphasis on communal and collective rights. The African Commission on Human and People's Rights (ACHPR) has interpreted and applied Article 24 in plethora of cases, one of which is *The Social and Economic Rights Action Center (SERAC) & ANOR v Nigeria*¹¹, also known as the *Ogoni case*. This case involved the environmental destruction in the Niger Delta due to oil extraction by Shell and the Nigerian government. The African Commission ruled that the Ogoni community had suffered violation of their rights to health (Article 16) and to a general satisfactory environment favourable to development (Article 24) due to the Nigerian government's failure to prevent pollution from oil exploration in the community and ecological degradations of their lands. More importantly, the court held that the right to a satisfactory environment under the Charter can be invoked in Nigerian domestic courts since the Charter has been incorporated into Nigerian domestic law. The decision reinforced that states have positive obligations to protect the environment and prevent harm to people's well-

¹⁰ C Okeke, 'Environmental Rights as Constitutional Rights: Nigeria's Legal Evolution' <<https://oal.law/environmental-rights-as-constitutional-rights-nigerias-legal-evolution/>> Accessed 7 April 2025

¹¹ (2001) AHRLR 60

being.¹² Although Article 24 seems to qualify the protection of the environment with development; it is nonetheless an affirmation of environmental rights in Africa. The ACHPR through its interpretation in landmark cases, it has strengthened the legal framework for environmental justice in Africa.

3.1.5 The Harmful Waste (Special Criminal Provisions) Act

This Act was enacted in 1988 in response to the illegal dumping of toxic waste in Koko, Delta State, by an Italian company. The Act criminalizes the improper handling, disposal, and movement of harmful waste to protect both the environment and public health. Section 6 provides for a punishment of life imprisonment for offenders as well as the forfeiture of land or anything used to commit the offence. Section 7 makes provision for the punishment accordingly, of any conniving, consenting or negligent officer where the offence is committed by a company. Section 12 defines the civil liability of any offender; he would be liable to persons who have suffered injury as a result of his offending act. The Harmful Waste (Special Criminal Provisions) Act contributes to environmental protection in Nigeria, it should be strengthened to recognize environmental rights more explicitly and enhance enforcement mechanisms.¹³

3.1.6 The Petroleum Industry Act

The Petroleum Industry Act (PIA) 2021 and its predecessor, the Petroleum Act, while primarily focused on regulating the oil and gas industry, have provisions related to environmental protection and potentially lead to environmental rights breaches through pollution. It promotes public safety and environmental protection. The Act was originally enacted in 1969 to regulate petroleum exploration and production in Nigeria. Section 9 (1) (b)

¹² KSA Ebeku, 'The Right to a Satisfactory Environment and The African Commission' (2003) 3 (1) *AHRLJ* <https://www.ahrlj.up.ac.za/images/ahrlj/2003/ahrlj_vol3_no1_2003_kaniye_sa_ebeku.pdf> Accessed 29 January 2025

¹³ Ibid

provides authority to make regulations on operations for the prevention of air and water pollution.¹⁴ The PIA seeks to provide legal, governance, regulatory and fiscal framework for the Nigerian oil & gas industry. The PIA addresses gas flaring and pollution in several sections. This section also outlines penalties for non-compliance, as prescribed by the Flare Gas (Prevention of Waste and Pollution) Regulations. Specifically, Section 104 prohibits gas flaring, and Section 105 prohibits flaring and venting of natural gas. Additionally, Section 105(2) grants the Nigerian Upstream Petroleum Regulatory Commission (NUPRC) the right to take gas destined for flaring free of charge. Sections 104 and 105, along with the Flare Gas (Prevention of Waste and Pollution) Regulations, outline penalties for non-compliance.¹⁵

3.1.7 The Oil in Navigable Waters Act

This act was enacted as a result of the International Convention for Prevention of Pollution of the Sea in 1954. It may be said that the most comprehensive legislation on oil pollution in Nigeria is the Oil in Navigable Waters Act No. 34 of 1968.¹⁶ It is concerned with the discharge of oil from ships. Section 1(1) prohibits the discharge of oil from a Nigerian ship into territorial waters or shorelines. Section 3 makes it an offence for a ship master, occupier of land, or operator of apparatus for transferring oil to discharge oil into Nigerian waters. It also requires the installation of anti-pollution equipment in ships. Section 6 makes punishable such discharge with a fine of N2,000 (Two thousand naira). Section 7 requires the records of occasions of oil discharge.¹⁷

¹⁴ Environmental Law Research Institute (n9)

¹⁵ Alliance Law Firm, 'Bridging the Gas Infrastructure Gap: The Implementation and Impact of the Petroleum Industry Act (PIA) 2021' <<https://www.lexology.com/library/detail.aspx?g=f5944006-9323-400f-b6c6-6ae0494c045d>> Accessed 31 May 2025

¹⁶ Oil in Navigable Water Act Cap 337, Laws of the Federation of Nigeria, 1990; L Atsegbua, V Akpotaire, and F Dimowo (n1) 29

¹⁷ Environmental Law Research Institute (n89)

3.1.8 The Associated Gas Re-injection Act

The Associated Gas Re-injection Act 1979¹⁸ deals with the gas flaring activities of companies in Nigeria. The following sections are relevant to pollution prevention; Section 3(1) prohibits, without lawful permission, any oil and gas company from flaring gas in Nigeria. Section 4 stipulates the penalty for breach of permit conditions.¹⁹ According to its preamble, this is an Act to compel every company producing oil and gas in Nigeria to submit preliminary programmes for gas re-injection. The Act appears good on paper, and worthy of commendation. It tries to reduce the flaring of gas, which affects the quality of the air. The Act itself merely exists on paper. Gas flaring ought to have ceased since 1984, however, it continues unabated.²⁰ It is worthy to note that this Act was promulgated to compel International Oil Companies to submit a plan on their gas utilization and re-injection programme by the following year. The Act has now been repealed by Section 310 of the Petroleum Industry Act, 2021 (PIA).²¹

3.2 Institutional Framework

3.2.1 The Judiciary

The Constitution and other state or federal laws established the Nigerian judicial system, which includes all courts. Other courts are not considered superior courts; only those created by the constitution are. Adjudication, legal interpretation, and the exercise of judicial review and supervision over administrative bodies are among the fundamental duties of the courts. They have jurisdiction over individuals, organizations, and businesses as well as actions that violate environmental regulations. The 1992 Rio Declaration's Agenda 21 calls on national governments to set up judicial and administrative institutions for legal remedies, highlighting

¹⁸ Associated Gas Re-injection Act Cap 20, LFN 2004

¹⁹ Environmental Law Research Institute (n9)

²⁰ L Atsegbua, V Akpotaire, and F Dimowo (n1) 41

²¹ AO2LAW, 'Current Gas Policies Challenges and Prospects' <<https://ao2law.com/current-gas-policies-challenges-and-prospects/>> Accessed 31 May 2025

the role of the legal system in environmental protection. Principle 10 calls on national governments to facilitate effective access to judicial and administrative proceedings, including redress and remedies, and to promote the involvement of all citizens who are affected. The Federal High Courts and the current High Courts have the authority to consider cases pertaining to environmental matters, despite the fact that Nigeria lacks a unique superior court of record with the sole authority to hear and decide environmental cases. For example, there are certain courts known as environmental courts at the magistrate court level in Cross River State. According to thorough investigations, the court was only designated as such by the Chief Judge of Cross River State and is not a unique legal creation for that purpose. They merely exercise criminal jurisdiction over those who are brought before it for breaching environmental sanitation exercise and other sanitation regulations of the state. Although there is no special superior court of record, existing High Courts and Federal High Courts have jurisdictions to address environmental issues.²²

Environmental litigations in Nigeria involve criminal prosecutions and civil litigations. Criminal prosecutions involve penalties such as monetary fines or imprisonment for violating environmental laws. Public authorities often institute these prosecutions, but there has been a lack of public litigations due to the attitude of Nigerian courts towards environmental issues and the lack of capacity of state prosecutors to handle them. For instance, Section 1(2) (c) of NESREA Act makes the agency capable of suing and being sued in its corporate name. Specifically, Section 8 (f) of the Act empowers the agency to establish mobile courts in collaboration with the relevant agency. The section provides thus: ‘subject to the provisions of the Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria, 1999, and in collaboration with relevant judicial authorities establish mobile courts to expeditiously dispense cases of violation of environmental regulations.’ It is the duty of the judicial system to convict, while

²² KSA Ebeku (n12)

it is the power of the agency to carry out such prosecutions. Section 32 (3) of the Act gives the agency powers to carry out such prosecution subject to the provisions of Section 174 of the CFRN 1999 as amended. Any officer of the Agency may, with the consent of the Attorney –General of the Federation, conduct criminal proceedings in respect of offences under this Act or regulations made under this Act. There has been paucity of public litigations in the form of prosecutions. The major reason for this is the attitude of the Nigerian courts to environmental issues as well as the lack of capacity of State prosecutors to adequately handle environmental prosecutions. The courts too have placed overriding economic benefits of the nation over environmental pollution. Civil litigations, on the other hand, are based on tortious liabilities or breaches of a duty of care imposed by law. They can be instituted by individuals, communities, corporations, and government institutions in cases of breaches of environmental legislations. A dominant form of environmental litigation in Nigeria is against oil pollution by individual citizens against oil companies. Regulatory institutions may also institute civil actions to obtain court orders for closing down premises in areas endangering the environment. Section 30 (1) (g) of the NESREA Act empowers the agency to obtain an order to suspend activities, seal and close down premises.²³

3.2.2 National Environmental Standards and Regulations Enforcement Agency (NESREA)

NESREA was charged with the responsibility of protection and developing the environment in general, and environmental technology, including the initiation of policies in relation to environmental research and technology, and to advise to government on environmental policies.²⁴ Furthermore, under the NESREA Act, the Agency is empowered to establish programmes for the prevention, reduction and elimination of pollution of the nation's air,

²³ SA Fagbemi and AR Akpanke, 'Environmental Litigation In Nigeria: The Role of the Judiciary' (2019) *NAUJILJ* 10 (2) <<https://www.ajol.info/index.php/naujilj/article/download/183681/173038>> accessed 16 February 2024

²⁴ Section 2, NESREA Act 2007

land, inter-state waters, as well as programmes for the restoration and enhancement of the nation's environment.²⁵ They oversee environmental protection regulations, including pollution control.

3.2.3 The Attorney-General

The Attorney General of Nigeria plays a vital role in enforcing environmental laws and protecting environmental rights. The Attorney General of Nigeria, who also serves as the Minister of Justice, plays a crucial role in enforcing environmental laws and protecting environmental rights. As the chief legal officer of the country, the Attorney General provides legal guidance on environmental policies, prosecutes environmental offenders, and ensures that Nigeria complies with both national and international environmental laws. Section 32 (3) of the NESREA Act gives the agency powers to carry out such prosecution subject to the provisions of Section 174 of the CFRN 1999 as amended. Any officer of the Agency may, with the consent of the Attorney -General of the Federation, conduct criminal proceedings in respect of offences under this Act or regulations made under this Act'.²⁶ In the course of protection of citizens' environmental rights, the Attorney General defend citizens' right to a clean and healthy environment (though not explicitly stated in the Constitution), take legal action against companies and government agencies that violate environmental rights, supports litigation on behalf of communities affected by environmental degradation (e.g., oil spills in the Niger Delta). The Attorney General also performs oversight of environmental litigation such as representing the government in environmental lawsuits, including cases against multinational corporations, works with state Attorneys General to enforce

²⁵ Sections 7 & 8 of NESREA Act 2007; L. Atsegbua, V. Akpotaire, and F. Dimowo, *Environmental Law in Nigeria: Theory and Practice* (2nd Edn, AMBIK Press, 2010) 115

²⁶ SA Fagbemi and AR Akpanke (n21)

environmental laws at the state level, and provides legal backing for environmental regulatory agencies like NESREA and the Federal Ministry of Environment.²⁷

²⁷ BE Umukoro and MO Omozue, Prosecuting Environmental Pollution Cases in Nigeria: The Head of a Carmel Passing Through the Eye of a Needle (2024) 3 (1) *PPLRUNLAWREVIEW* <<https://runlawjournals.com/index.php/pplrunlaw/article/view/100>> accessed 3 May 2025

CHAPTER FOUR

DISCUSSION AND ANALYSIS

4.1 The Enforceability of Environmental Rights in Nigeria

Environmental rights refer to the entitlements of individuals and communities to a clean, safe, and healthy environment. In Nigeria, environmental rights are increasingly significant due to persistent pollution, deforestation, oil spills, and other forms of environmental degradation. Despite their importance, the legal framework for protecting environmental rights in Nigeria is complex and often criticized for its weak enforcement mechanisms. The inadequacy of existing legal mechanisms to protect man and the environment from the incursions of modern technology necessitated the clamour for the recognition of environmental rights as a separate and distinct right.¹ Although environmental protection is deemed important by Nigeria's constitution, the enforceability of environmental rights is hindered by the fact that Section 20, which requires environmental protection, is a part of Chapter II, which is deemed non-justiciable, meaning it cannot be directly enforced in court. The position that the right to a safe and clean environment is an absolute right that should be guaranteed in a sane society without any compromise supports the inherent commitment to environmental protection and sustainability. Protecting environmental rights is critical for upholding human dignity, as a clean and safe environment is necessary for living a life of dignity and worth.² The courts have developed an innovative constitutional framework for environmental protection in response to this ongoing environmental catastrophe. This jurisprudential evolution marks a

¹ L Atsegbua, V Akpotiare, and F Dimowo, *Environmental Law in Nigeria: Theory and Practice* (2nd Edn, AMBIK Press, 2010) 167

² I Ezenwa, 'The Right to a Safe and Clean Environment with Regard to Oil Pollution and Climate Change in Nigeria' <<https://www.mondaq.com/nigeria/clean-air-pollution/1567434/the-right-to-a-safe-and-clean-environment-with-regard-to-oil-pollution-and-climate-change-in-nigeria>> accessed 7 April 2025

significant departure from traditional common law and statutory remedies, establishing environmental rights as fundamental human rights deserving constitutional protection.³

This paper further explains the status of environmental rights under the Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria 1999 as amended and their legal enforceability. It begins by affirming the supremacy of the Constitution under Sections 1(1) and 1(3), as upheld in *Abacha v Fawehinmi*⁴, and questions whether the Constitution protects the right to a safe, habitable, and healthy environment. Environmental protection provisions are found in Chapter II, particularly Sections 13, 17, and 20. Section 13 mandates all arms of government to uphold the principles in this Chapter, including environmental welfare. Section 20 obligates the state to protect and improve the environment. However, Section 6 (6) (c) renders Chapter II non-justiciable, meaning its provisions cannot be enforced in court, as reiterated in *Morebisha v Lagos State House of Assembly*⁵. Despite this, Chapter IV, which contains justiciable rights, may offer indirect protection. Section 33(1) guarantees the right to life, and it is arguable that severe environmental degradation may endanger life, thus violating this enforceable right and right to dignity (Section 34) have been invoked to argue for environmental justice. Environmental rights in Nigeria involve both the right to a safe, healthy environment and the right to legal redress when these are violated. While Chapter II provides the framework, enforceability must often rely on creative interpretation of justiciable provisions like the right to life in Chapter IV.⁶

³ AB Abdulkadir, 'The Right to A Healthful Environment in Nigeria: A Review of Alternative Pathways to Environmental Justice in Nigeria' (2014) 3 (1) *ABU: JSDLP* <<https://www.ajol.info/index.php/jsdlp/article/download/122619/112167>> accessed 7 April 2025

⁴ (2001) 51 WRN 29

⁵ (2000) 3 WRN 134

⁶ OVC Ikpeze and NC Anyachebelu, An Examination Of The Environmental Rights And Sustainability In Nigeria (2023) 19 (3) *UNIZIKLJ* <<https://journals.ezenwaohaetorc.org/index.php/ULJ/article/download/2692/2818>> accessed 7 April 2025

When one thinks of environmental rights infringement, our minds may go to the pitfalls of the oil exploration processes and companies and how they have affected the environment. Regardless, there are other clear cut examples of environmental pollution which may result environmental rights infringement. Some of which are; dumping of refuse recklessly especially in rivers, creeks, gutters, etc., and the effect of this particularly in the Southern part of Nigeria is the obstruction of the flow of water in these water bodies. In most cases, people tend to suffer from the impact of this during the flood season. Below is a pictorial illustration of environmental pollution which is a violation of human rights.

Fig. 1.2 The Obunagha-Tunama Bridge, Yenagoa, Bayelsa State

4.2 The Concept of Environmental Rights Infringement in Nigeria and the Legal Implications under the Nigerian Law

In most common law systems, environmental liability has developed from actions under tort to fundamental rights actions. In between this development, legislatures in common law countries have enacted and amended statutes that stipulate environmental liability and enforcement. It is logical to imagine that an unhealthy environment will have negative impacts on lives and property, which are protected fundamental rights in most countries. It is also desirable for a system to have multiple avenues available for the enforcement of sound environmental practices and processes.⁷ Thus, the infringement of environmental rights is simply the violation of those rights. Hence, the section will lay focus on the legal implications of the infringement of environmental rights under the Nigerian law.

Right to Life

The right to environment, in so far as it related directly to the existence of man and his survival, occupies the same position and importance as the constitutional right to life. This is because a poor, dirty and putrid environment can affect the health of the individual and result in subsequent death. Hence there is no doubt that polluted environment affects the health, mental, as well as physical welfare of human beings and therefore, survival has become difficult due to change in physical, chemical and biological conditions of the environment. The discharge of effluents into the atmosphere, oil spills, gas flaring, dumping of refuse, acid rains are some of the instances of pollution that have considerably affected the quality of human life. Section 33(1) of the CFRN 1999 as amended provides as earlier posited that ‘every person has a right to life’. Thus, a person’s right to life is breached when as a result of a polluted and degraded environment his life is cut short. The duty to protect life rests squarely on the state, and this duty encompasses the obligation to prevent situation that might

⁷ A Babalola, ‘The Right to a Clean Environment in Nigeria: A Fundamental Right?’, 26 (1) *HELJ* <https://repository.uchastings.edu/hastings_environmental_law_journal/vol26/iss1/2> accessed 19 April 2025

imperil human life. The state is not only obliged to refrain from taking life intentionally, but also to take adequate steps to safeguard it. Furthermore, the right to life being the most important of all human rights implies the right to live without deleterious invasion of pollution, environmental degradation and ecological imbalances as posited in *M.C. Mehta v Union of India*⁸. The right to life provided for under Article 6(1) of the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights (ICCPR) 1966⁹ is largely affected by the polluted environment. This has led to the development in various countries of the concept that right to healthy environment is a fundamental human right implicit in the right to life.¹⁰ In the case of *Jonah Gbemre v SPDC*¹¹, The Federal High Court has ordered oil companies and their workers to stop gas flaring in the Niger Delta, as it violates guaranteed constitutional rights to life and dignity. The court held that Mr. Jonah Gbemre had authority to represent himself and the community, and that the fundamental rights to life and dignity, as guaranteed by Sections 33 and 34 of the CFRN 1999, include the right to clean, poison-free, pollution-free environments. The court also found that the respondents' failure to conduct Environmental Impact Assessments in the applicant's community violated their human rights. The ruling also aligns with the African Charter on Human and Peoples' Rights (Ratification and Enforcement) Act.¹²

Right to Dignity of the Human Person

Section 34(1) of the CFRN 1999 as amended, guarantees the right to dignity of the human person. Although the Constitution does not expressly guarantee the right to a clean or healthy environment as a fundamental right, environmental degradation and pollution can

⁸ (1987) AIR 1086

⁹ ICCPR 1966

¹⁰ E Emenike, MA Ebikake – Nwanyanwu, and C Ajie 'Right To A Healthy Environment In Nigeria And Other Jurisdictions: A Legal Assessment' (2020) 8 (3) *GJPLR*
<<https://www.eajournals.org/wp-content/uploads/Right-to-a-Healthy-Environment-in-Nigeria-and-Other-Jurisdictions.pdf>> accessed 10 April 2025

¹¹ (2005) 6 AHRLR 152

¹² E Emenike, MA Ebikake – Nwanyanwu, and C Ajie (n10)

significantly impact human dignity. Consequently, it is possible to situate environmental rights within the framework of existing fundamental rights, especially the right to dignity. This provision emphasizes the inherent worth of every individual and seeks to protect against conditions or actions that degrade the quality of human life. In interpreting this provision, it is increasingly argued that environmental degradation, particularly when it results in displacement, health hazards, and loss of livelihood, may amount to inhuman and degrading treatment, thereby constituting a violation of this right. Environmental pollution, such as oil spills, gas flaring, toxic waste dumping, and industrial emissions, has been a persistent problem in many parts of Nigeria, especially the Niger Delta. These conditions have led to widespread contamination of air, water, and soil, thereby undermining the health, wellbeing, and socio-economic stability of affected communities. Where individuals are forced to live in polluted environments without access to clean water, air, or safe housing, their dignity as human beings is compromised. Such conditions strip individuals of their ability to live a meaningful and healthy life, which lies at the core of the right to dignity.¹³

Right to Property

The right to own property is one of the human rights, and it is made a fundamental right by the 1999 constitution. This right to own property has a wide scope, which includes the right to own moveable and immovable property such as animals, plants, buildings, etc. The citizen's right to own property can be eroded in the sense that a misuse of the environment, which leads to damage of the ecosystem resulting in acid rain, ozone layer depletion, global warming, gully erosion, earthquake, flooding, desertification and vibration from construction works or Seismic operation, etc., causes the death of animals, plant, and even damage to buildings. Environmental pollution through oil spillages destroys properties such as crops, fishponds, economic trees. The derogation of the right to property of individuals, families and

¹³ E Emenike, MA Ebikake – Nwanyanwu, and C Ajie (n10)

communities is buttressed in the case of *Otoko & Ors v Shell B.P.*¹⁴ Where the escape of large quantity of oil polluted drinking water, killed fishes and marine life and desecrated the plaintiffs' Juju Shrine. The above case shows the human rights of persons to own property can be affected by a degradation of the environment.¹⁵ The legal implications of these infringements include long-term public health crises, economic disempowerment of affected communities, and increased litigation against corporations and government agencies. While Nigerian law recognizes the importance of environmental protection, the legal framework for enforcing environmental rights remains weak. Without making environmental rights justiciable and enhancing enforcement mechanisms, environmental degradation and the infringement of citizens' rights will continue unabated. Strengthening legal protections is essential not only for environmental sustainability but also for safeguarding public health and social justice.¹⁶

4.3 The Problems/Challenges of the Enforcement of Environmental Rights in Nigeria

The 1979 Constitution established a conflict between the Federal High Court (FHC) and State High Courts (SHCs), especially in environmental cases involving oil and gas. Conflicts arose because the 1979 Constitution gave the FHC exclusive jurisdiction while granting SHCs unlimited jurisdiction. In order to address this, the 1999 Constitution gave the FHC exclusive jurisdiction. Nonetheless, jurisdictional problems still exist, especially in environmental cases, where the FHC is ill-prepared and lacks expertise. Access barriers for rural victims are caused by the small number and dispersed location of FHC divisions, which compromises environmental justice.¹⁷ Besides jurisdictional issues, proving environmental pollution cases in Nigeria poses significant challenges due to their technical nature. Although the burden of

¹⁴ (2005) 9 NWLR (Pt 931) 439

¹⁵ E Emenike, MA Ebikake – Nwanyanwu, C Ajie (n10)

¹⁶ Ibid

¹⁷ BE Umukoro and MO Omozue, 'Prosecuting Environmental Pollution Cases In Nigeria: The Head Of A Carmel Passing Through The Eye Of A Needle' (2024) 3 (1) *PPLRUNLAWREVIEW* <<https://runlawjournals.com/index.php/pplrunlaw/article/download/100/82>> accessed 10 April 2025

proof follows the civil standard—balance of probabilities—victims often need expert scientific evidence to establish causation and damage. However, most victims, particularly in rural areas, cannot afford expert witnesses, leading to many dismissed claims, as illustrated in cases like *Ngbor v Compagnie Generale De Geophysique*¹⁸ and *Seismograph Services v Ogbeni*¹⁹. Courts often blame lawyers for failing to secure expert testimony, but the real issue lies in victims’ financial incapacity. Critics argue that strict adherence to traditional rules of evidence unfairly disadvantages pollution victims. Some progress has been made, such as the Supreme Court’s recognition of public interest standing in *Centre for Oil Watch v NNPC*²⁰, which opened the door for human rights-based litigation. Legal scholars like Ladan suggest applying doctrines like *res ipsa loquitur* and *Rylands v Fletcher*²¹ to presume liability in pollution cases, especially where the defendant controls the source of harm. The courts have occasionally adopted this approach, inferring negligence when facts point clearly to the defendant’s responsibility. Therefore, without systemic reform—both legal and institutional—victims of environmental pollution will continue to face significant obstacles to justice.²²

Another major challenge faced by victims of environmental pollution is that of the principle of locus standi, which directly affects the enforcement of environmental rights. Locus standi is Latin for ‘place of standing’, and it simply means ‘the right to bring an action or to be heard in a given forum’. This rule is aimed at preventing claimants with remote or no interest all from approaching the court. In *Adesanya v President of FRN*²³, the Court in describing the

¹⁸ Unreported Suit No. BHC/30/93

¹⁹ (1976) 4 S.C 85

²⁰ (2019) 5 NWLR (Pt 1666) 517

²¹ (1886) L.R 1 Ex. 265

²² BE Umukoro and MO Omozue (n17)

²³ (1981) 2 NCLR 358

concept referred to Section 6 (6) (b) of the 1979 Constitution²⁴, which is the same with Section 6 (6) (b) the CFRN 1999 as amended. Establishing a party's locus standi is owed to the fact that where the plaintiff lacks the locus standi to institute a legal proceeding, the court will rightly decline the jurisdiction to consider it. In *Oronto Douglas v Shell Petroleum Development Company and Ors.*,²⁵ the claimant sued defendants for allegedly breaking the Environmental Impact Assessment Act in connection with a liquefied natural gas project in Rivers State. Because the claimant lacked the legal capacity to file the lawsuit and there was no evidence of a violation of rights or a conflict of interest, the court dismissed it. First is the need to prevent professional litigants, or meddlesome interlopers from using the court's jurisdiction for cases that may not directly affect them. Second is protecting and encouraging the desire of individual citizens to participate in the enforcement of the law actively. However, the Nigerian judiciary seems to have applied a stringent interpretation of the locus standi rule. This has significantly affected the enforcement of environmental rights in the country. Locus standi is a legal technicality that prevents victims of environmental rights violations from accessing justice. The courts should endeavour to play a more proactive role, lowering the requirements for locus standi in the interests of justice.²⁶

4.4 Remedies for the Infringement of Environmental Rights under the Nigerian Law

Generally, the remedies given for environmental liability comes in form of fines, penalties, compensations, etc. Chapter IV of the Constitution provides for fundamental rights in order to give effect to the protection and enforcement of the rights protected therein. Section 46 (3) of the Constitution, on the other hand, provides the power to make rules regulating the procedure for the enforcement of these rights. Accordingly, Fatayi-Williams, former Chief Justice of Nigeria (as he then was), brought into existence the Fundamental Rights

²⁴ CFRN 1979

²⁵ (1998) LPELR-6457

²⁶ BE Umukoro and MO Omozue (n17)

(Enforcement Procedure) Rules 1979²⁷ which became operative from the 1st day of January, 1980. The Rules applied to fundamental right proceedings until 1st December 2009 when new rules (i.e. Fundamental Rights (Enforcement Procedure) Rules 2009) were introduced by Idris Legbo Kutigi,(CJN as he then was) bringing in so much changes into fundamental rights proceedings in Nigeria. A major change brought about by these Rules can be found in the objectives of the Rules. Paragraph 3(a) and (b) of the Preamble provides that the principal objectives of the Rules is that the fundamental rights provisions of the Constitution and the African Charter, are to be applied and interpreted purposefully and expansively in order to advance and realize the rights and freedoms contained in them and afford the protections intended by them. The Rules equally enjoin the Courts to respect relevant international and regional treaties in applying the Rules. These objectives presuppose that the rights and freedom contained in the African Charter, for instance, are litigable as fundamental rights to which the FREP Rules 2009 are applicable. The FREP Rules 2009, ordinarily, should bring a sigh of relief to advocates of environmental rights in Nigeria since Article 24 of the Charter on Human and Peoples' Rights recognizes the right of "all people... to a general satisfactory environment favourable to their development. Unfortunately, the courts are yet to accept that Article 24 of the African Charter Act falls outside the non-justiciability clause in the 1999 Constitution. Thus, environmental rights advocates have not been able to advance their arguments for the enforcement of environmental rights under the FREP Rules in Nigeria beyond the constitutional limitation in Section 6 (6) (c) of the CFRN 1999 as amended. It has been observed that Chapter IV of the 1999 Constitution having been duplicated in the African Charter Act, it is only those provision of the Charter reproduced in Chapter IV that are enforceable. Apparently, the right to satisfactory environment contained in Article 24 of the African Charter is not one of those rights contained in the fourth Chapter of the Constitution

²⁷ FREPR 1979

which provides for fundamental rights in Nigeria. However, from the provisions of the FREP Rules 2009 it can be gathered that it is not the intendment of the rules that application for fundamental rights enforcement be limited to Chapter IV of the Constitution. This can be deduced from Order 9 Rule 1 of the FREP Rules 2009.

From the underlined, this paper posits that the FREP Rules deliberately include the African Charter in the 2009 Rules for the purpose of enforcement. The rules unequivocally provide that Chapter IV of the Constitution and the African Charter shall be expansively and purposely interpreted and applied. The 2009 Rules provide for the commencement of Fundamental Right cases by interest group and third parties thereby abolishing the time-honoured principle of locus standi as far as cases under those rules are concerned. Paragraph 3(e) of the Preamble to the 2009 Rules allows applications to be filed by others on behalf of the actual person whose rights are affected. While this provision is in line with the Supreme Court decision in *Centre for Oil Pollution Watch v NNPC*²⁸ on the issue of locus standi, whether environmental rights are actionable as fundamental rights is still a huge academic debate in Nigeria. The Supreme Court in this case held that public-spirited individuals and NGOs can institute environmental public interest lawsuits on behalf of third parties even when such NGOs and individuals have not suffered any damage or injury whatsoever. The case was brought in the Federal High Court, Lagos Division, over an oil spillage in Acha Community of Abia State of Nigeria. The oil spillage was allegedly caused by the defendant's negligence resulting from its pipeline, which had corroded due to lack of maintenance, had ruptured, fractured and spewed its entire Contents of persistent hydrocarbon mineral oil into surrounding streams and river of Ineh/Aku, resulting in contaminating two community streams that were the major sources of water supply to the

²⁸ (2019) 5 NWLR (Pt. 1666) 517

community. The plaintiff alleged that although the defendant contained the spillage on the surface, it failed to clean up or reinstate the Ineh/Aku streams/river. Furthermore, the plaintiff averred that the respondent was negligent in both the causation and containment of the oil spillage; that the spillage had harmful effect on living resources, marine life, human health and other usage of the streams. The respondent challenged the plaintiff's standing to sue and sought an order striking the suit. On February 9, 2006, the trial court struck out the suit for lack of locus having not suffered any injury at all, let alone any injury above every other member of the Acha community resulting from the alleged oil spillage. On January 28, 2013, the Court of Appeal dismissed the appeal by reaffirming the trial court's ruling. The plaintiffs appealed to the Supreme Court on March 9, 2013. On July 20, 2018, the Supreme Court unanimously granted the appeal in favor of the appellant. The SC further held that the appellant NGO had the standing to sue the respondent, thereby liberalizing or broadening the rule of standing. The Supreme Court specifically highlighted that public spirited individuals and organizations can bring an action in courts against relevant public authorities and private entities to demand their compliance with relevant laws and to ensure the remediation, restoration and protection of the environment. The Supreme Court decision in the above case aligns with the Constitutional Human Rights approach to Environmental and Climate Protection taken earlier by the Lower Court/Federal High Court in *Jonah Gbemre v SPDC*²⁹ and others. It demonstrates a significant positive paradigm shift in the attitude of the Supreme Court to environmental and climate change related claims. It provides additional human rights and constitutional tools for potential climate litigation in Nigeria. The Supreme Court also made significant strides in 'greening' the Nigerian Constitution and confirming the existence and enforceability of environmental human rights in Nigeria, in a manner that increases the possibility of successful climate change litigation in the country, especially by

²⁹ (2005) 6 AHRLR 152

allowing public interest litigation. First, the Supreme Court held that Section 20 of the Nigerian Constitution on duty to protect the environment by the State is justiciable when read together with, and in the context of, a provision like Section 4(2) of the Constitution, on the power to make laws to give effect to Section 20. Second, the Supreme Court explicitly recognized for the first time, that Section 33 of the Constitution which guarantees the Right to Life implicitly includes and constitutes a fundamental right to a clean and healthy environment for all. Third, the Supreme Court explicitly affirmed the enforceability of the environmental right in Article 24 of the African Charter on Human and Peoples' Rights as domesticated in Nigeria by the African Charter Act, Cap.³⁰ The Supreme Court also acknowledged that recognizing public interest litigation will help address some other barriers to access to justice, as poor communities without 'the financial muscle to sue' which usually and disproportionately bear the brunt of environmental and climate change problems, will have the benefit of public spirited persons and organizations fighting their cause.³¹

If the provisions of FREP Rules are recognized as applicable to environmental rights claim, that will be a great relief to poor victims of environmental pollution who do not have the means of prosecuting expensive environmental pollution cases. The rules also suggest that applicants can file representative action and same would not be struck out on the argument that applicants cannot litigate separate causes of action collectively. Going by these Rules, NGOs and other public spirited individuals are at liberty to approach the Court on behalf of any person whose fundamental rights are affected or threatened either by any individual or by the government. Unfortunately, these threats do not include threats posed by environmental pollution. There is a dire need for an amendment of the Constitution to include environmental rights in the fourth chapter, particularly by reviewing. Section 46 (1) of the Constitution

³⁰ African Charter Act, Cap. A9 LFN 2004

³¹ BS Ramos , 'Environmental Public Interest Litigation in Nigeria: The Paradigm Shift in COPW v. NNPC' (2020) 3 *EULJ* <<http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4824748>> accessed 31 May 2025

which at the moment limits the enforcement of fundamental rights to those rights stated in Chapter IV alone. Extending the FREP Rules to environmental rights claim is a huge breakthrough for the advancement of environmental rights and a great respite to applicants who ordinarily are not able to fund the full blown trial process of environmental pollution cases under the common law of tort. By Order 2 Rule 2 of the FREP Rules 2009, fundamental rights cases can be commenced by originating motions or originating summons or by other modes accepted by the court. The 2009 Rules abolish the application of limitation laws with regards to fundamental rights proceedings. In addition, both the FHC and the SHC have concurrent jurisdiction to hear fundamental rights cases. Thus, if the right to clean environment is recognized as fundamental right in Nigeria, procedure for prosecuting environmental claims will benefit the objectives of environmental protection laws more and will restore the confidence of those seeking to approach the courts for environmental claims to ventilate their grievances.

4.5 Constitutional Provisions for Environmental Rights in other Climes in comparison to Nigeria

In recent decades, the acknowledgement and defence of environmental rights within constitutional frameworks have become more and more important on a global scale. Many nations have responded by incorporating environmental clauses into their constitutions because environmental degradation and climate change represent serious challenges to sustainable development, public health, and fundamental human rights. This comparative study examines other nations' constitutional protections for environmental rights and assesses how well they stack up against Nigeria's own. Through constitutional reform, it aims to

strengthen environmental governance in Nigeria by highlighting best practices, pointing out gaps, and providing insights.³²

In Canada, the Province of Ontario has enacted an Environmental Bill of Rights which provides for the right to a healthful environment³³. In June 2023, the Canadian Environmental Protection Act, 1999 (CEPA) was amended and modernized. With these changes, the Government of Canada recognizes, in the preamble, that every individual in Canada has a right to a healthy environment as provided under CEPA. The Government of Canada also has a duty to protect the right to a healthy environment when making decisions under the Act. The amendments confirm the Government's commitment to implement the United Nations Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples, which will be implemented in consultation and cooperation with Indigenous Peoples.³⁴ In *E.H.P v Canada*³⁵, Canadian residents alleged that radioactive wastes that remained after the government had conducted a cleanup constituted serious risks to health in violation of Article 6 of the ICCPR.³⁶ In the U.S.A, there is statutory rule of strict liability for oil pollution under the Federal Water Pollution Control Act 1972. The right to a clean environment asserted in the United Nations Commission on Human Rights has been judicially recognized in India and in the Pakistani case *Shela Zia v Water and Power Development Authority*³⁷. In this case, a group of citizens sued and obtained a Supreme Court judgment stating that, the right to life included a right to live in a clean environment. This case further addressed the construction of a dam on the Indus River which posed a threat to the mangrove forests of the Indus Delta. Thus, relying on the India/Pakistan court decisions, individuals/communities in Nigeria should exercise the

³² L Atsegbua, V Akpotaire, F Dimowo, *Environmental Law in Nigeria: Theory and Practice* (2nd Edn, AMBIK Press, 2010) 204-207

³³ Ibid

³⁴ Government of Canada, 'A Right to a Healthy Environment under the Canadian Environmental Protection Act, 1999' <<https://www.canada.ca/en/environment-climate-change/services/canadian-environmental-protection-act-registry/right-to-healthy-environment.html>> accessed 7 April 2025

³⁵ CCPR/C/17/D/67/1980

³⁶ L Atsegbua, V Akpotaire, and F Dimowo (n29)

³⁷ PLD 1994 S.C. A16

right to a clean environment under the fundamental rights provision in Section 33 of the CFRN 1999 as amended. Article 9 of the Constitution of Pakistan recognizes the right to life, which has been interpreted to include the right to a healthy and pollution free environment. The United Kingdom has no constitution in the strict sense of the word. Nevertheless, there are a number of provisions under the English law which gives individuals rights in respect of the environment. The right which propose to falls under three general categories, these include:

- i. Enforcement through injunction whereby the offending party is either restrained from doing something or ordered to do something in respect of the environment.
- ii. Public participation and consultation in the licensing process, most importantly under the Town and Country Planning Act 1990.
- iii. Rights for individuals to prosecute criminal offences in the field of environmental law.

Section 24 of the Constitution of the Republic of South Africa enshrines environmental rights; this right is interpreted to have a twofold purpose. The first part guarantees a healthy environment while the second part mandates the State to ensure compliance with the first part mentioned above.³⁸ This paper further compares the approach to environmental protection under the Ghanaian and Nigerian Constitutions. Both countries include environmental objectives in their respective Directive Principles of State Policy; Article 36(9), Article 41(k), and Article 37(3) in Ghana and Chapter II in Nigeria, but these provisions are generally considered non-justiciable, meaning they cannot typically be enforced in court. However, recent Ghanaian Supreme Court cases suggest a shift. In *New Patriotic Party v Attorney-General*³⁹, Justice Adade argued that the entire Constitution is justiciable, including the Directive Principles, since Articles 1(2) and 2(1) allow any law inconsistent with the

³⁸ L Atsegbua, V Akpotaire, and F Dimowo (n29)

³⁹ Ghanaian Supreme Court decision of 19th December, 1993, Unreported 1996/907 SCGLR 726.

Constitution to be struck down. Thus, it is now arguable that Ghanaian courts can enforce environmental rights found in the Directive Principles when these rights are connected to constitutionally guaranteed, justiciable rights.⁴⁰

⁴⁰ L Atsegbua, V Akpotaire, and F Dimowo (n29) 204-207

CHAPTER FIVE

CONCLUSION

5.1 Summary of Findings

Human rights and the environment are intrinsically intertwined: a safe, clean, healthy and sustainable environment is essential in the enjoyment of our human rights; whilst polluted, hazardous and otherwise unhealthy environments potentially violate our human rights. From a legal point of view, pollution is the wrongful contamination of the atmosphere or of water or of soil, to the material injury or damage to the rights or property of people. Man as a living being is entitled to live in a clean healthy environment devoid of contamination and pollution from industrial waste and other technology induced interferences with the environment. Pollution occurs in relation to many uses and activities of man, including the mining, exploration and use of petroleum and its by-products. In all these cases, there is damage to marine life, wildlife habitat, farmland, shrines, recreational beaches, property and other social amenities. Apart from these instances, there are health hazards and threats to life, as well as the destruction of natural amenities upon which are based the economic and social wellbeing of the inhabitants of these areas.¹

Environmental rights mean any proclamation of a human right to environmental conditions of a specified quality. More than 100 countries incorporate constitutional rights to a healthy environment. When environmental rights are violated, people and the planet suffer from reduced health and well-being.² The right to healthy environment is not expressly guaranteed by the 1999 Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria. However, Sections 13 and 20 of the Constitution has to do with environmental concerns. Though, Section 20 of the

¹ A Babalola, 'The Right to a Clean Environment in Nigeria: A Fundamental Right?' (2020) 26(1) *HELJ* <https://repository.uclawsf.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=1576&context=hastings_environmental_law_journa l> accessed 3 August, 2024

² Geneva Environment Network, 'Human Rights and the Environment' <<https://www.genevaenvironmentnetwork.org/resources/updates/human-rights-and-the-environment/>> accessed 7 April 2025

Constitution might appear to confer the right to a healthy environment, the right is not justiciable as a result of the provisions of section 6(6) (c) of the constitution. Therefore, a litigant cannot institute an action in a Nigerian Court for a violation of his/her right to a healthy environment pursuant to section 20 of the Constitution. It is worth noting that the African Charter, particularly Articles 22 and 24, which Nigeria has ratified and domesticated recognizes this right. The African Charter links the right to a healthy environment with the right to development. It may be deduced from the foregoing that the International recognition of the right to a healthy environment entails both a right for everyone to benefit from the environment as well as an obligation for all to manage it sustainably and enforce its sustainability. It is possible to canvass alleged breaches of the Charter before Nigerian courts since it has been domesticated. Thus, the rights embodied in the charter are 'legal rights', the alleged breach of which a High Court has jurisdiction to entertain under the constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria.³

5.2 Recommendation

The details discussed below are the recommendations for the effective enforcement of environmental rights in Nigeria. Firstly, the 1999 Constitution of Nigeria should be amended, in order to confer the right to a clean and healthy environment as a fundamental right, independent of other rights which should be made enforceable in any High Court of the Federation, as is the practice in countries such as South Africa, India. In other words, the right to a healthy environment should be elevated to the status of fundamental right as it is obtainable in other jurisdictions of the world like India, Spain, Ethiopia, Uganda, etc. by including it in Chapter IV of the CFRN 1999 as amended so that victims of environmental abuse can easily approach the court to enforce this right when it is infringed upon. The provision of Section 20 should be made justiciable as it is obtainable in India where the

³ A Babalola (n1)

provision was transplanted from and implanted in the 1999 Constitution as amended. The doctrine of locus standi should be liberally applied or totally removed in respect of environmental litigation in order to make it easy for victims of environmental degradation to approach the court to ventilate their grievances. Victims of environmental degradation should ensure service of pre-action notice on prospective defendant(s) before approaching the court to ventilate their grievances if that is the condition precedent for the institution of legal action against an environmental abuser. This will prevent their suits from being struck out in the event service of pre-action notice is a condition precedent for the actuation of the jurisdiction of the court. Environmental litigants should not sleep over their rights for too long without approaching the court to institute legal proceedings to protect their rights as doing so could make statute of limitation caught up with their claim.⁴ The Government at all levels should take the protection of the environment with more seriousness than it currently is by enacting legislations which give life to the right to a clean and healthy environment pursuant to its law-making powers. Nigeria should domesticate other International instruments which recognize the right to a healthy environment to which she is a party, such as the Universal Declaration on Human Rights, International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights, International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights, etc. The Associated Gas Reinjection Act should be amended to criminalize gas flaring, and allow for no consent level of gas flaring. Mitigating and remediating the damages to the environment attendant from oil exploration, production and distribution activities. An applicant seeking to enforce environmental rights as fundamental rights under chapter IV of the Nigerian Constitution can use locus standi, which is friendly to public interest suits, and the Supreme Court's liberalization of the concept of standing with respect to public interest environmental actions. The applicant must prove that the environmental act or omission has deprived or is capable of

⁴ EJ Ekpenyong and EF Ekpo, 'Access to Justice in Environmental Law in Nigeria: Challenges and the Way Forward' (2022) 6 (1)*AJIEEL* <<https://ajieel.com/index.php/a/article/view/29/39> 55-65> accessed 13 May 2025

depriving persons of their lives and/or immovable properties, based on compelling evidence. The case should be one for Chapter IV - Sections 33 and/or 43 of the Nigerian Constitution. There are three options for an applicant to enforce the right to a clean environment as a fundamental right in Nigeria:

- i. Enforce the right to general satisfactory environment and the corresponding duty of the State to protect and improve the environment under the African Charter by way of an Application recognized by the FREPR.
- ii. Seek a Chapter IV (Right to Life and/or Property) constitutional action, arguing that environmental actions or omissions that have deprived or are likely to deprive persons of their lives and immovable property are subsumed under the right to life and property.
- iii. The ECOWAS Court is situated in Abuja, Nigeria, and is therefore an effective place to litigate fundamental rights actions pursuant to the African Charter or other international human rights treaty. However, a litigant that pursues this option is limited to suits based on international human rights treaties and against Nigeria or the Community Institutions.

Lastly, afforestation should be encouraged, so as to prevent the indiscriminate felling of trees that could expose the environment to drastic ozone layer depletion thereby resulting to climate change.⁵

5.3 Conclusion

The Federal Government of Nigeria should be mindful of maintaining clean and healthy environment as key issues to sustainable development and happiness of the citizens of the nation in accordance with International best practices as provided in various Conventions. It is obvious that the solution to healthy environment will never be realized by formation of

⁵ A David, 'Environmental Pollution- A Violation Of Human Rights <https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=4954250> accessed 3 May 2025

Commissions, for example the OMPADEC, which has been scrapped, or the NDDC which is currently experiencing financial setbacks or more recently, the NESREA and the NOSDRA established before it. Suffice it to state that in event of any environmental pollution and degradation that adequate compensation as of right must be paid to the affected people as well as effective machinery being put in place to restore the affected environment back to its prior condition as much as practicable. Unfortunately the provision on environment in the Nigerian Constitution not yet generally accepted as justiciable obviously because of conflicting constitutional provisions. Therefore, in order to align with the Supreme Court judgement in *Abacha v Fawehinmi*⁶, there is need for immediate amendment of the Nigerian Constitution to make the provisions for environmental protection justiciable so as to provide easy access to justice on environmental issues.⁷

⁶ (1994) NWLR (Pt 306) 1

⁷ NG Ikpeze, 'The Environment, Oil and Human Rights in Nigeria' (2024) 2 (15) *NAUJILJ* <<https://www.ajol.info/index.php/naujilj/article/download/82388/72543>> accessed 29 January 2025

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